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D8.2 Final report on Transnational Access 1

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D8.2 Final report on Transnational Access 1

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement

Executive summary

This document aims to present an overview of the Transnational Access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 8 (WP8) TA1 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for rehabilitation as part of the VITALISE project. This final report encompasses six (6) research infrastructures that participated in the context of this work package, presenting information for completed TA activities.

In particular, the report includes comprehensive information for each of the participating research infrastructures. It provides a summary of completed TA activities of every research project, the activities performed, the outcomes achieved, and any notable findings or advancements made. In addition, the report for the completed TA activities includes also some information regarding the effort and hours spent from the several professionals of the LL personnel for supporting the execution of each TA activity, both in person and remotely, as well as a summary of the researchers' TA evaluation and potential opportunities for future collaboration and common publications. This information showcases the value and impact of the TA program on the overall project objectives.

As it is the final report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP8's TA1. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of rehabilitation and collect all the information generated in the different TA activities 1.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP8

WP8 deals with the centralised and coordinated design and implementation of transnational access for infrastructures related to the rehabilitation domain in VITALISE. Under transnational access we refer to the usage of VITALISE infrastructures by users located in other countries than the location of the respective accessed infrastructure. This WP information is linked to the activities and information collected in WP9 and WP10.

VITALISE infrastructures are fully open to all users that have a clear and significant research objective. For each infrastructure there is an estimated access of 30 days for each project that can be performed either physically or remotely.

The research infrastructures participating in WP8 are the following ones:

- AUTH, Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by AUTH
- THOMAS MORE Motion Lab, Mobilab & Care (M18-M36) led by LiCalab
- GAIA, Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation (M18-M36) led by GAIA
- INTRAS, rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by INTRAS
- LAUREA Simulated Hospital (M18-M36) led by LAUREA
- McGill, CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by McGill

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M18-M36 of the VITALISE project regarding the Transnational Access (TA) to research infrastructures. This document includes the performed TA activities and additional information for planned activities (in case of defined for some of the TA). The report is linked to the activities and information collected in the Transactional Accesses of WP9 and WP10, having the same structure as D9.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 2" and D10.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 3" and. The final reports completed by the visiting research teams could be provided upon request to the following e-mail: vitalise-helpdesk@googlegroups.com

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 8 (WP8), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Finalised Transnational Access Projects)** provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, description of the activity, services used, evaluation from researchers, and some information about the number of hours/days spent by the Living Lab personnel.
- **Section 3 (Analysis)** offers a reflective analysis including overall LL experience of the Living Labs in relation the TAs, distilling lessons learnt from these engagements, then providing insights about the impacts and experience gained throughout the process.
- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Transnational Access projects

This section initially presents the overall evaluation results in TA calls and the overall evaluation results after TA as analysed from the responses of visiting researchers to the “After TA evaluation questionnaire” answers of the Transnational Access to the WP8 Living Lab infrastructures.

In addition, this section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP8 Living Lab infrastructures.

2.1 Overall results in TA calls

The following infographic offers information regarding the number of the TA for WP8. The infographic includes aggregated information from the three (3) VITALISE Open calls, taking into account all requested projects.

In the infographic below the Transnational Access activities performed within WP8 are presented. The number of participants reached is 33, from which 2 TAs were cancelled due to personal reasons and 4 members of 2 research teams (ID23 and ID44) did not participate due to personal reasons. From the 33 total number of applicants 13 were males and 20 females, achieving a great proportion of gender balance and inclusivity. Furthermore, the research domains of the applicants are presented, with almost 65% coming from academia and 21% coming from industry. The working countries of the applicants are also presented. The TAs performed within WP8 reached applicants from 12 different working countries in Europe and Latin America. In particular, we reached applicants from Hungary, Germany, Slovenia, Austria, Italy, Bulgaria, Belgium, Ireland, Israel, the Netherlands, Argentina and Colombia.

Figure 1: Vitalise TA WP8

2.2 Overall evaluation results

The evaluation of the visiting researchers' experience from the TA to the Rehabilitation LL Infrastructures presented below, is based on their feedback provided through the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire”, which they were required to complete individually, upon concluding their research studies. These questionnaires, developed by VITALISE partners on the EUSurvey platform prior to the TA Open Calls, were distributed to participating researchers via a provided link for completion. We received a total of 17 responses in the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire” from the 21 participants in the TA to the Rehabilitation LL Infrastructures.

The analysis of the responses shows an overall positive experience. All 17 responders answered 7 or above to the first question (“How likely are you to recommend Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)”). We also calculated the Net Promoter Score (NPS), asking respondents to rate the likelihood of recommending the TA experience to colleagues. The NPS is calculated by subtracting the Detractors from the Promoters. Promoters are considered those who answered above or equal to 9, Passives are those that answered from 7 to 8 and Detractors are those who answered below or equal to 6. Twelve (12) out of seventeen (17) responders, approximately 71% were promoters and there were zero (0) detractors. This results in an NPS equal to 71 (Figure 2).

The participants were also asked to rate how well their expectations were met, on a 5-point Likert scale (much higher, higher, as expected, lower, much lower). The total percentage of expectations met is 88.23% (15 out of 17) that reflects the responders who answered, "much higher", "higher" or "as expected". More precisely, six (6) participants stated that the output was "as expected", three (3) participants responded that they experienced a higher output and six (6) participants responded that they experienced a much higher output. Two (2) responses were “much lower” and “somewhat lower”.

In terms of quality, the analysis of the services provided shows that the rating is mostly high, with very few neutral and none low or very low responses in each category. The questions that were analysed were those of section 6: “Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality”. The services were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from very low to very high, also providing the NA option. The services rated were the following:

1. Methodological support and guidance,
2. Physical infrastructure,
3. Expertise/support with end users,
4. Understanding of end-user needs and problems
5. Selection/recruitment of research participants

Each question of section 6 represented one service. The percentage of “very high” and “high” answers was the most common, with very few “neutral” answers and none “very low and “low”” answers. The Overall Satisfaction percentage was based on the answers to all the questions that were related to the quality of services. More specifically, we counted all the instances of High and Very High answers to all 5 questions related to the quality of services (74 answers in total, 11 NA values). Sixty-three (63) out of seventy-four (74) responses (85.1%) declared a positive attitude (high or very high satisfaction) for the services provided.

The following dashboard (Figure 2) contains the data visualizations of the analysis conducted on the questionnaires in terms of quality and satisfaction of the TA visiting researchers.

Figure 2 Quality of services provided by the TA LL infrastructures.

Further analysis of the answers to the fourth (“What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7.B What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of the visited research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study?”) open questions, led to the discovery of the TA key strengths, as reported by the researchers. The responses were analysed using qualitative content analysis. Coding the main points of each answer and grouping them based on common elements, we eventually concluded in the following four (4) categories that represent the TA key strengths.

1. Networking.
2. Research opportunities.
3. Learning opportunities.
4. Professional development.

Accordingly, following the same method described above, we analysed the answers to the fifth (“Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7C. What weaknesses in the visited research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity”) open questions, resulting to the following three (3) TA suggestions for improvement:

1. Streamline Bureaucratic Processes.
2. Optimize Survey Requirements.
3. Increase funding.

Additionally, the answers to open questions thirteen (“Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research?”) and fourteen (“Any additional comments you would like to share with us?”) complemented the strengths or the suggestions of the categories mentioned above.

2.3 Presentation of the TA research projects

This section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP8 Living Lab infrastructures. For each TA research project, we have included a dedicated session for the following aspects:

PROJECT SUMMARY

Background, set objectives, adopted research methodologies and principal results achieved.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

Reflects on the conclusions drawn from each TA project, and on the immediate aftermath of the TAs and ventures into potential future collaborations and researcher evaluations.

TA EVALUATION

Reflects on researchers’ evaluation and feedback and present the LL personnel dedicated efforts including hours spent, extracted from the TA monitoring Excel spreadsheet, the Excel file where all the LLs were reporting the hours spent by both LL staff and researchers for the realization of each TA project separately. Regarding the LL personnel dedicated efforts, the total sum of hours spent by all the LL staff members supporting the execution of each TA project (both in person and remotely) was calculated. The total number of person days was calculated by counting and summing the total days where the indicated hours were above 0 for each LL staff member.

2.4 AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 1 Status TA in AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation living lab

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	N° of researchers	Visit performed
23	25/07/2023 - 04/08/2023 & 22/01/2024 - 01/02/2024	project planning and management, concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study, and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation. Equipment and facility rental service; Expert opinion, and advisory services	24 days	19	2	YES
95	24/10/2023 - 23/01/2023	project planning and management, concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study. Equipment and facility rental service; Expert opinion, and advisory services.	76 days	37	1	YES

ID23 Understanding neuromuscular adaptations in increased gravity with the short-arm human centrifuge

Researcher: Uros Marusic (Lead Applicant)

Number of researchers: 2

Period: 25/07/2023 - 04/08/2023 & 22/01/2024 - 01/02/2024

Project summary

This interdisciplinary project aimed to push the boundaries of research on sensorimotor processing and performance changes with increased gravity gradients using a short-arm human centrifuge. The primary objectives include identifying neuromuscular mechanisms underlying these changes and using Mobile Brain/Body Imaging (MoBI) instrumentation to access unprecedented behavioural and neural data analysis. By utilizing this advanced technology, the project sought to develop MoBI assessment protocols for increased gravity conditions, which could have significant applications in countering spaceflight deconditioning and developing interventions for long-duration spaceflights.

Moreover, the study aimed to shed light on the clinical improvements observed in patients exposed to centrifuge therapy, potentially leading to the development of new treatments for various ground-related pathologies. The transfer of knowledge between Greek and Slovenian teams was a key aspect, with the potential for common publications and piloting on hospitalized patients. The installation of a short-arm centrifuge in Slovenia in 2021 to support hypoxic bed rest campaigns opened future collaboration opportunities for the teams to apply their expertise in centrifuge research, thereby increasing their chances of participating in future ESA calls.

Overall, this ambitious project held the promise of advancing the understanding of sensorimotor processing, gravity induced effects, and potential medical applications for patients, while also fostering international collaboration and knowledge exchange between Greek and Slovenian researchers

Objective of the project:

This project aimed to advance research using a short-arm human centrifuge to study the acute effects of centrifugation on sensorimotor processing. The main objectives were to compare the neurophysiological responses of stroke patients exposed to higher G-gradients. By using state-of-the-art neurophysiological equipment and advanced imaging techniques, the project sought to gain a comprehensive understanding of how sensorimotor processing and performance are affected by increased gravity gradients. The potential outcomes of this study could be instrumental in developing personalized centrifugation procedures for hospitalized patients.

The setup of the project was to subject consenting stroke patients to 5 centrifugation cycles in different gravitational levels (1,5G, 1,7G, 2,0G, 2,2G and 2,5G). During the activity, the subjects were equipped with a portable, 32 channel EEG machine. Each cycle lasted approximately 7 minutes, 6 minutes of performing the EEG paradigm once the desired G-level was reached and 1 minute approximately for the centrifuge to reach the desired G-level.

The auditory oddball paradigm that was employed had the following characteristics: 200 non-target sounds at 1000Hz and 50 target (oddball) sounds at 1500Hz. The stimuli duration was 200ms and the interstimulus interval varied between 900 and 1400 ms. Before the initiation of the trail, the subjects were presented with 5 target and 5 non-target sounds. The paradigm was passive.

Subjects:

The subjects that took part in the study were adults that had suffered one or more strokes. All subjects had already participated in the VITALISE JRA study, so no acclimation with the centrifuge was necessary. Five subjects agreed to take part in the study.

For the purpose of this TA, 2 researchers Uros Marusic and Ahac Istenic from the SCIENCE AND RESEARCH CENTRE KOPER, Slovenia visited the premises of the AUTH Rehabilitation and Human Centrifuge Living Lab in different time-points. The first visit took place between 24th July 2023

and 4th August 2023. During this first visit, Uros Marusic came to the LL to implement the EEG protocol and test the functionality of the equipment. At the end of this visit, the target participants were identified and all necessary arrangements had been made to carry out the actual data collection in 2024. The second visit took place between 22nd January 2024 and 26th January 2024 for Ahac Istenic and 29th January 2024 to 1st February 2024 for Uros Marusic. During these visits, the researchers performed the data collection. The 3rd researcher of the Slovenian team, Ana Mali could not attend the visit, so she participated virtually, and her place was filled by the AUTH research team. Four participants took part in the data collection phase. The original plan was for 10 to be able to obtain results of statistical significance. The rest of the participants will be recruited and measured by the AUTH team in the future, and the results will be collectively analysed and published. Here, only the results of the first participant are included.

The EEG data were loaded and the channel DC03, the one providing the triggers, was checked. Each time the amplitude of this channel was above 60, an “STIM” marker was inserted.

Figure 3 raw signal with no markers (left), raw signal with “STIM” markers inserted (right)

Next, the file with the channel position was loaded

Figure 4 Channel location.

To clean the signal of artefacts, a preprocessing consisting of a High Pass and a Low Pass filter, leaving signal in the range of 05Hz to 40Hz was performed, followed by Independent Components Analysis to remove eye and muscle components, when present.

Figure 5 ICA components

After visual inspection of the clean data to make sure that no more artefacts were present, all conditions were loaded:

'lying_PRE', 'lying_POST', 'centrifuge_1_7', 'centrifuge_2_0', 'centrifuge_2_5'

The conditions were concatenated to run filtering, visual inspection and ICA on all files together, to remove the same amount of information for all conditions. The data were then re-referenced to the average electrode and epochs from -200ms to 800ms were extracted with baseline 200ms from -200ms to 0ms.

Figure 6 plot of different electrodes in all conditions. FP2 (top left), F3 (top middle), Fz (top right), O2 (bottom left), T4 (bottom middle), T6 (bottom right)

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The first results look promising towards the brain response to auditory potentials during centrifugation in different G-levels for stroke patients. More participants are needed to extract statistically significant results, so the data collection will continue. Differences between target and non-target sounds will be explored, offering insights on the effects of artificial gravity in the human brain.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was actually also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), one technical expert, one doctor, and two data analysts were involved. In total, approximately 203 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of this project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 25 person days.

Overall, the feedback from the researchers on their experience in the AUTH Living Environment Simulation was very positive. All researchers reported that the outcomes of the TA were as expected if not somewhat higher, and that they are very likely to recommend the Transnational Access to their colleagues or other researchers. The researchers also felt that the inclusion of the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful, and they rated highly the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance. Two of them suggested streamlining the administrative processes and increasing communication channels to increase the efficiency of the access. The key strengths of this experience that the researchers reported to have valued most were the AUTH research team who supported them with professionalism throughout the realization of their project, as well as the access to the unique LL infrastructures and research facilities.

ID95 Assessment of the therapeutic effects of SAHC on lymphedema patients

Researcher: Jack Van Loon (Lead Applicant)

Number of researchers: 1

Period: 24/10/2023 - 23/01/2023

Project summary

The application of 'short-arm centrifugation' (SAHC), also called 'gravitational therapy' (GT), has been reported as a beneficial therapy in both primary and secondary lymphedema patients by reducing oedema, improving mobility and skin sensitivity of the lymphedematous limb and by reducing the frequency of erysipelas episodes. However, the mechanisms through which SAHC contributes to lymphedema improvement are not fully understood and require further investigation.

The present cohort study consisting of 10 patients will be conducted at the AUTH Centrifuge & Rehabilitation Living Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. Inclusion criteria for this study are adult patients (>18 years of age), with primary or secondary ISL stage 2a lymphedema of the arms or legs (International Society of Lymphology). Excluded from this study are patients with malignancies, metastases, advanced neurological disorders or psychiatric disorders, epilepsy, pregnancy, existing arrhythmia, recent surgery (within 6 months), recent bone fractures (unless referred by a physician), participants taller than 2 meters.

Patients undergoing the SAHC treatment will be trained at various g levels, three times a week, for a total of 20 sessions. Each centrifugation session will last for a total of 72 minutes, divided into sections of 15 minutes with 4-minute pauses in between. Specific lymphedema assessments will be performed prior to, during and following the 7-week SAHC period. The patient's limbs will be assessed for typical signs of lymphedema such as pitting or nonpitting, oedema, dorsal hump, square toes, Kaposi-Stemmer sign, lymphorrhagia, and skin changes. A single researcher will measure limb circumference for objective volume assessment prior to, during and following the SAHC-treatment. Patients will be asked to fill in the LYMPH-ICF-UL questionnaire, a PROM questionnaire evaluating functional impairment, before and after the 7-week period to assess changes in function, symptoms, appearance, quality of life or psychological well-being. Photographs of the patient's limbs will be taken prior to and following the SAHC-treatment.

Objective of the project:

The primary aim of the study described is to assess whether a 20-session treatment with short-arm centrifugation (SAHC) will significantly improve short-term therapeutic outcomes, such as quality of life, arm circumference, arm function and lymphedema symptoms, in patients with ISL stage 2a lymphedema (International Society of Lymphology).

To realise this project, one researcher, Daphne Van Gemert visited the AUTH Rehabilitation and Human Centrifuge LL between 23rd October 2023 and 17th December 2023. The rest of the research team chose a virtual access to the infrastructure and participated in regular meetings overlooking the whole procedure. The research team identified the importance of a prolonged data collection period and decided to fund the rest of the project (apart from the one month covered by the Vitalise project) from their own funds.

Once the researcher arrived in Greece, the preparation for the ethics committee application was initiated. The application was rejected by the committee, so the timeline of the project pushed back. The researcher reapplied to the committee, but the application was again rejected, resulting in the non-realisation of the project. During her stay in Greece, the researcher got accommodated with the infrastructure, prepared for the analysis of the data with the help of the AUTH experts' team but could not complete the study. The application was rejected twice due to infrastructure reasons, since the ethics committee considered this specific intervention therapeutic and they pled non-responsible for carrying out such a protocol with this specific infrastructure, which is built and registered for non-therapeutic purposes.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The external research team still believe in the strength of the proposed research and the importance of it being carried out. As a result, once the issue of the ethical committee is resolved they aspire to acquire funding to visit the infrastructure and perform their research.

TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was actually also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), one technical expert, one doctor, and two data analysts were involved. In total, approximately 190 hours were spent by all the mentioned professionals for supporting the realization of this project in AUTH Living environment simulation, both in person and remotely, which is translated to more or less 24 person days.

Overall, the feedback from the researchers on their experience in the AUTH Living Environment Simulation was kind of positive. All researchers reported that the outcomes of the TA were much lower than expected, due to the inability of actually carrying out their research, but they declared that they are likely to recommend the Transnational Access to their colleagues or other researchers. The researchers also felt that the inclusion of the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful, and they rated high the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance. The recruitment received a low rating due to its non-realization. They were all disappointed with the non-completion of their study but realized that the issue was administrative and not on the part of the AUTH team. The key strengths of this experience that the researchers reported to have valued most were the AUTH research team who supported them with professionalism throughout the procedure.

2.5 THOMAS MORE Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care

This section presents a summary of LiCalab’s TA projects. Two projects involving four researchers made use of this research infrastructure (ID43 & ID57). Project ID57 was selected to present their research at the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024.

Table 2. Status TA in Thomas More Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care

Project name	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA DAYS REMOTE/	TA DAYS PERSON	Number of researchers	Visit performed
ID43	Visit 1 MAY 23 Visit 2 OCT 23 Visit 3 MAR 24	Equipment and facility rental service; Expert opinion, and advisory services; Prototyping test; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	6	15	2	Visit 1 & 2 performed, visit 3 planned end of March 24

ID57	Visit 1 OCT 23 Visit 2 JAN 24	LL project planning and management, concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study, and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	90	7	2	YES
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Note. ID 57 combines the use of the THOMAS MORE Motion lab infrastructure with the LiCalab older adults' homes. In terms of KPIs it is only counted as being part of Thomas More Motion lab.

ID43 Dynawork: Smart uniform testing

Researcher: Sabri Mahdaoui (Lead applicant), Assen Tchorbadjieff, Bulgaria.

Number of researchers: 2

Period: Visit 1 MAY 23, Visit 2 OCT 23, Visit 3 MAR 24

Project summary

Background and objectives

Ergonomics is the science of fitting workplace conditions and job demands to the capability of the working population. The goal of ergonomics is to reduce stress and eliminate injuries and disorders associated with the overuse of muscles, bad posture, and repeated tasks. A workplace ergonomics program can aim to prevent or control injuries and illnesses by eliminating or reducing worker exposure to risk factors using engineering and administrative controls. Risk factors include awkward postures, repetition, material handling, force, mechanical compression, vibration, temperature extremes, glare, inadequate lighting, and duration of exposure.

Ergonomic Assessments are mostly carried out manually by an expert, but it seems that this old-fashioned approach gives poor results, consumes time, covers just some small period of the working activity of the operator and angles are estimated on a feeling.

Dynaback's objective is to make the process simple and automated. Dynaback is a uniform with integrated sensors in textile for motion capture, that can be worn on the work floor.

Research methods

During the first visit in May 23, the algorithms of the Dynaback t-shirt were optimized comparing them with the validated Captive Motion system of Thomas More Motion lab (TEA CAPTIV T-Sens Motion (IMU)). During the five days a synchronization test was conducted. Participants were Thomas More employees as well as the TA researcher. A picture of these research activities conducted in the Thomas More Motion lab can be found in **Error! Reference source not found..** First, the ideal position of the back sensor was determined. Then, measurements were performed concerning zero position, isolated movements of the upper limbs (both static and dynamic), more complex movements of the upper limbs, movements from the risk tool EAWS (European Assembly Worksheet) used to identify ergonomic risk factors, and finally movements related to particular professions such as painting or writing on a black board etc. Human movement data while performing professional tasks was collected using the Dynaback suit and the validated IMU sensors simultaneously. The data was

translated into a set of parameters, which were linked to risk and as for example described in existing, RULA, OCRA index, RULA, KIM manual actions, HARM, strain index. Analyses of the risky movements were performed per joint.

Figure 7. Professional movements in the lab

During the second visit, LiCalab and Mobilab&Care collaborated with Dovre, a Belgian company based in Weelde that has its own large iron foundry. Dovre is specialised in the development, production and sale of fireplaces and stoves made of high-quality cast iron. Seventeen employees of the factory wore the Dynaback shirt while performing their physically demanding work. Every employee wore the shirt at least twice on the same work station. Data was collected and all workstations were reviewed and discussed with the safety officer of the company.

During the final visit in March '24, all results that have been analysed at that point will be discussed with two Dovre safety officers and the plant manager of the company. Ideas for future research will be examined.

Results and conclusion

In general, the following general data issues are available now (Dynaback and Captiv):

1. Some of the computed from both systems raw parameters require additional filtering. They are required because there are blind spots in both systems. For example, some particular movements in Captive frontal and sagittal projections data are detected in both directions. For Dynaback shirts' current version, for instance, walking interfered with some parameters data, such as *back lateral*, as spikes. For correction of these issues, additional filtering by data removal based on multidimensional coincidence detection is required. There is a developed data filtering implementation for major issues in Dynaback's data, but it is not separated in distinct tool.
2. The calibration flagging in Dynaback is used as an important detector of irregularities in data. It consists of flagging between 0 and 3, where 0 shows absolute data divergence. There are several experiments, mainly during the first day, which clearly failed due to not completed calibration. The main effect on data is wrong measurements, including systematic bias, wrong angles, etc. There are some cases when the operator was doing quick brisk movements and calibration flagging is degraded from 3 to 2 until back to 3 after a while. Despite that no systematic classification of error severity is done and resulting data de-basis, there is a possibility that the higher calibration index

values (as 2 and probably 1 in some cases) could be corrected and recomputed values used as valid. The major issue with data validity when calibration index is equal to 2 is the amplitude bias, but movement detection remains detected.

3. The data is synchronised and compared using video. After synchronisation, the data from both sensors are compared visually and Dynaback sensors are verified for calibration status. The generated plots are shown as combined plot of two sensors data in parallel in combination with related calibrations flags. The flags range is between 0 and 3, where boundaries are marked with dashed lines.

An example of a measurement, namely the *EAWSMovements test*, is provided below as a detailed illustration of the comparison between Dynaback and Captiv data.

In general, this test covers shoulder flexion while body is moving by bending forward or sideways (lateral). The results in sagittal plane between both systems are absolutely identical (Figure 8, top).

However, there are differences between both systems data in frontal plane (Figure 8, bottom) The main explanation is that the data are plotted in different projections. The Dynaback data shows projection on frontal plane. The Captiv system represents projections by frontal plane adjusted by projections on transverse plane. However, there are extra unexplained spikes in the Captiv data. This implies an additional issue with data interpretation.

Figure 8: Sagittal plane data for right (top) and left (bottom) from the EAWS Movements experiment

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Algorithms of the Dynaback shirt have been optimised after comparison with validated Captive motion measurements of the Thomas More Motion lab. This way, measurements performed with Dynaback will be more valid and reliable. The researchers plan to perform extra measurements in the future, f.i. using insoles or shoes in collaboration with Thomas More research group Mobilab&Care.

TA evaluation

The researchers indicated that the TA outcome was much higher than expected. They especially appreciated the ability to discover lab equipment and test it. Key strengths of LiCalab, Mobilab&care and the Thomas More Motion lab are the expertise in setting up the protocols as well as the available test equipment. Sabri used the Vitalise websites several times during his TA. The other Vitalise tools were not relevant for their project. He indicated that the website was very user friendly, but scored neutral in terms of usefulness.

LiCalab and Mobilab&Care staff committed to this project comprised one operations manager, one researcher-psychologist, one engineer-physiotherapist, one researcher-engineer, one doctor in industrial engineering, and one doctor in biomedical sciences. Because the last visit is planned for the end of March we make an estimation for the hours spent by our staff during those final days. In total 152 dedicated hours are spent by our staff on this project. It was split up in three research visits. Most of the time was spent on the actual testing of participants in the Motion lab. The amount of hours the Dynaback shirt was used in the factory was not counted for because our staff was not present during this remote data collection phase.

ID57 Physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women,

Researchers: Oonagh Giggins (Lead applicant), Suzanne Smith, Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dublin Road, Dundalk, Co Louth, Ireland.

Number of researchers: 2

Period: Visit 1 OCT 23 Visit 2 JAN 24

Project summary

Background and objectives

This research seeks to address the issue of physical inactivity and functional decline in mid-life-menopausal women. Physical inactivity is a global health issue, with one in four adults not meeting the recommended target levels for physical activity. Physical activity is reported to decline with advancing age, and middle-aged women are more vulnerable to become physically inactive with the menopausal transition. Regular physical activity results in many health benefits and is an important determinant of physical performance.

Poor physical performance is a predictor of frailty, disability and loss of independence and the menopause transition has been shown to be associated with decreased functioning.

The **aim** of this TA is to examine physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women and examine whether the menopause is associated with an accelerated decline in physical function and physical activity levels and increased musculoskeletal issues.

To achieve the aim of this research, the following **objectives** have been identified:

- To undertake an examination of physical capability among mid-life (peri-menopausal, menopausal, or post-menopausal) women.
- To capture a quantitative physical capability dataset in this cohort using body worn sensors and compare sensor measurements with measurements obtained using traditional means.
- To characterise daily physical activity levels in the same cohort over a 3-month period.
- To examine differences in physical capability, physical activity and musculoskeletal issues across menopausal stages

Research method

This research will firstly involve a cross-sectional study and then a subsequent longitudinal study, to determine the physical activity levels and physical capability of a cohort of mid-life women who are also experiencing musculoskeletal problems.

Data collection:

- **Demographics**
- **Physical health:** heart rate at rest, blood pressure, weight, body mass index and percentage body fat. Self-reported past medical history (including obstetric and gynaecologic history), use of medications, presence of musculoskeletal disease or conditions, lifestyle related factors (smoking habits, alcohol consumption and daily physical activity levels).
- **Quality of life:** Menopause Rating Scale (MRS)
- **Pain:** the McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ)
- **Menopause status** (WHO classifications)
- **Physical capability tests:** Timed Up & Go Test (TUG), the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), postural stability tests, gait speed tests, and grip strength test.
- **Physical activity:** Withings smart watch: Daily physical activity levels (step count) and sleep

Figure 9: Physical capability testing: The grip strength test

Results and conclusions

Ten female volunteers (age: 56.7 ± 6.3 years, weight: 66.6 ± 7.1 kg, height: 163.8 ± 4.6 cm) took part in the investigation. According to the WHO definition of menopause status, one participant was pre-menopausal, one peri-menopausal, and eight were classified post-menopausal. A descriptive analysis of the data is presented in this report. The group mean (SD) for each of the physical health and physical capability measurements are presented in Table 3. Table 4 outlines each participants' MRS score and MPQ as well as each participants average daily step count over the 3-month monitoring period. Further analysis will be performed to investigate the relationship between physical activity, physical function and MSP and quality of life. These insights will in the long run improve quality of life in (peri)menopausal women.

Table 3. Group mean and standard deviation for measures of physical health and physical capability.

	Heart Rate	Systolic Blood pressure	Diastolic Blood Pressure	Grip Strength Left (kg)	Grip Strength Right (kg)	Six-minute walk test distance (m)	Gait speed (m/s)
Mean (SD)	70 (12.2)	132 (16.4)	87 (8.5)	22 (5.3)	22 (4.3)	572 (80.3)	1.3 (0.1)

Table 4. Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) and McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ) scores as well as Three-month average daily step count for each participant.

Participant ID	MRS	MPQ	3-month daily step count
P0	18	24	8599
P01	17	62	8299
P02	21	24	5568
P03	33	65	5719
P04	26	59	7724
P05	16	42	10808
P06	24	61	5779

P07	22	29	7463
P08	31	42	10293
P09	17	19	11337

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The data is currently being analysed to examine the relationship between physical activity levels and functional capacity and pain and quality of life in this cohort of midlife women. This work is a precursor to future work which will be undertaken by the applicant, which aims to develop a digital physical activity intervention for middle-aged, menopausal women. This project will have a range of impacts, across the short to long term, in areas of national and global health and wellbeing policy. The main output from this work will be the generation of a quantitative physical activity and physical function dataset which will be used to inform the development of a new digital platform targeting an increase in physical activity and a decrease in sedentary behaviour. This has the potential to have a positive impact on middle-aged women who use the intervention, enabling them to take active control of their health and well-being. Although menopause is a normal ageing process, the hormonal changes in this period of life may lead to many physical, physiological and social changes, resulting in deteriorations in quality of life. Increasing physical activity in this cohort may decrease menopausal symptoms and improve quality of life. Empowering middle-aged women to take responsibility for their health and wellbeing by becoming more physically active, may also reduce their risk and/or prevent the onset of a number of chronic health conditions such as coronary heart disease. This research has therefore the potential to make a significant long-term impact on population health if adopted.

TA Evaluation

Oonagh declared that the TA output was much higher than expected. She very much enjoyed the opportunity to work in a different institution and collect data using equipment she otherwise does not have access to. Additionally, she loved to broaden her network and gain a deeper understanding of the benefit of adopting a living lab approach to her research. According to Oonagh, key strengths of LiCalab are the physical infrastructure of the Motion Lab and access to participants (through a large panel). During the TA she made use of the Vitalise website and Wiki page, which she found very user friendly and evaluated neutrally in terms of usefulness.

Thomas More LiCalab and Mobilab&Care staff involved in the current project consisted of one operations manager, one panel manager, one researcher-psychologist, one physiotherapist with an additional degree in engineering, one Matlab expert, and one electromechanical engineer. A total of 166 dedicated hours was spent on this project. Most of the time was devoted to defining the research protocol and writing Matlab codes. Ethical approval was obtained by the applicant in Ireland. Not much intervention was needed during the 3-month remote data collection period.

2.6 GAIA- Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation

Table 5. Status TA in GAIA Ocean living lab for rehabilitation

Project name	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA DAYS REMOTE/	TA DAYS PERSON	N ^a of researchers	Visit performed
ID69	March 2024 (2-11)	Expert opinion and advisory services. Stakeholder analysis	20	10	1	YES

		and mapping, LL project planning and management. Co-creation session				
ID84	January 14 th February 2024 15 th	Expert opinion and advisory services. Stakeholder analysis and mapping, LL project planning and management. Co-creation session.	30	31	1	YES

ID69 Performing Arts-Smart space. Population well-being and climate change relationships

Researcher: Alon Meiri (lead applicant), Israel

Number of researchers: 1

Period: 2-11 March 2024

Project summary

Background and objectives

Public entities are nowadays trying to adapt public spaces to new uses addressed to new sociological needs. Ocean Living Lab is working in close collaboration with Gernika-Lumo municipality, with the participation of entities that work closely with civil society such as the City Council itself and Gernika Gogoratz, a Research Centre for Peace created by decision of the Basque Parliament in April 1987, coinciding with the 50th anniversary of the bombing of Gernika.

Our objective is to generate a space for dialogue, citizen-centred, generating an open innovation ecosystem based on an inclusive user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in a real-life community and setting. Make an analysis of the influence of climate environment in citizens’ well-being and the use of spaces.

Activities performed:

- Comparative analysis from experience in Israel (Eilat-Eilot innovations in renewable energy and Sharon region environmental unit) and Ozean living lab considering population’s wellbeing and climate change relationship and the use of public spaces.
- Participation in workshop with different researchers.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

For the conclusions and future outlook of the initiatives previous remote research was conducted by the researcher in collaboration with Ocean living lab.

The following information collects the comparative analysis from the different experiences.

Eilat-Eilot innovations in renewable energy vs Ocean living lab

After analysing the information regarding the Eilat-Eilot initiative in Israel and the GAIA Ozean Living Lab, we can draw a comparative analysis focusing on their support for people's wellbeing and the influence of climate change. These living labs offer innovative approaches to environmental and societal challenges, leveraging local ecosystems and community involvement.

Main Comparative Aspects

Geographical Focus and Climate Challenges: Eilat-Eilot operates in the Arava region, focusing on renewable energy solutions tailored to arid conditions and high solar potential.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab, part of the VITALISE project, is situated in a coastal area with rich biodiversity, focusing on sustainable innovation, including nature-based solutions to enhance climate resilience.

Innovation and Technology: Eilat-Eilot emphasizes renewable energy technologies, particularly solar energy, to combat global warming and promote sustainable development.

In contrast, GAIA Ocean Living Lab adopts a broad approach to open innovation, incorporating sustainable projects across cleantech, sports and tourism, and safety, with a significant focus on societal wellbeing and health through performing arts.

Community Engagement and Stakeholder Involvement: Both initiatives prioritize stakeholder involvement but with different approaches. Eilat-Eilot creates economic opportunities and educational programs to foster a renewable energy industry.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab, however, utilizes the living lab methodology to engage various stakeholders, including citizens, companies, public organizations, and researchers, promoting co-creation and open innovation ecosystems.

Sustainability Goals and Climate Adaptation: Eilat-Eilot aims for regional energy independence and carbon neutrality through renewable energy technologies.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab seeks to protect ecosystems, promote societal wellbeing, and support green economy development, directly contributing to climate adaptation and mitigation.

Conclusion analysis 1

Both the Eilat-Eilot initiative and the GAIA Ocean Living Lab demonstrate the critical role of innovative, community-engaged living labs in addressing climate change and promoting sustainable development. While Eilat-Eilot focuses more narrowly on renewable energy technologies to achieve its goals, the GAIA Ocean Living Lab adopts a broader approach to innovation, covering a wider range of sustainability and wellbeing projects. Both models, however, underline the importance of stakeholder engagement and co-creation in developing solutions that are tailored to local conditions and challenges.

Future Outlook analysis 1

Eilat-Eilot should continue expanding its renewable energy projects while exploring new ways to integrate these technologies into wider sustainability and climate resilience efforts.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab is poised to further explore the intersection of environmental sustainability with societal wellbeing, potentially expanding its focus areas to address emerging climate challenges.

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing between such living labs across different regions and climates could enhance the global response to climate change, leveraging unique local insights for broader applicability.

Technological and Methodological Innovations developed in these living labs could be scaled and replicated in other regions, guided by a shared commitment to sustainable development and climate resilience.

Sharon region environmental unit vs Ocean living lab

Following the same structure as the previous research a second analysis was carried out considering the Sharon region environmental unit and Ocean living lab experience. Previous analysis was made before the TA. During the visit the researcher could share with other researchers the insights and information analysed during this preliminary research. Considering the information collected by the Living Lab in Israel and the Ocean Living Lab, we can draw several comparative insights, conclusions, and look towards the future outlook regarding their support in people's wellbeing and the influence of climate change.

Main Comparative Aspects

Focus and Objectives: The Sharon Region Environmental Unit in Israel focuses on addressing climate change through a regional "living lab" that emphasizes smart and nature-based solutions for climate resilience.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab, as part of the VITALISE project, focuses on creating a sustainable open innovation lab that promotes the quality of life through environmental, social, and economic credentials, with a strong emphasis on healthcare, wellbeing, and utilizing natural capitals.

Innovation and Stakeholder Engagement: The Sharon Region initiative seeks to integrate urban and rural authorities for climate change adaptation, using a wide range of partners from government, academia, private sector, and civil society.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab utilizes living lab methodologies for stakeholder mapping, engagement, and co-creation among citizens, research organizations, companies, and government agencies, focusing on quadruple helix model of innovation.

Approach to Wellbeing and Climate Change: The Israeli Living Lab addresses wellbeing indirectly through its focus on environmental resilience and sustainable solutions to climate challenges.

GAIA Ocean Living Lab directly aims at promoting societal wellbeing and health, alongside environmental sustainability, showcasing a holistic approach to addressing climate change impacts.

Conclusion analysis 2

Both the Living Lab in Israel and the Ocean Living Lab offer innovative approaches to tackling climate change and enhancing people's wellbeing. While the Israeli Living Lab is more focused on environmental resilience and climate adaptation strategies, the Ocean Living Lab presents a holistic model that integrates societal wellbeing into its core mission of environmental sustainability. Both models exemplify the importance of stakeholder engagement and the utilization of living labs as a method for collaborative and innovative problem-solving.

Future Outlook analysis 2

Expansion and Replication: Both living labs highlight the potential for replicating their models in other regions facing similar climate and societal challenges. Future initiatives could benefit from the lessons learned in engaging stakeholders and integrating cross-sectoral approaches.

Increased Collaboration: There's potential for increased collaboration between different living labs globally, sharing insights, methodologies, and technologies to tackle climate change more effectively while enhancing societal wellbeing.

Innovation and Technology Development: As these living labs continue to evolve, there will be greater opportunities for developing and implementing new technologies and innovative solutions that address both climate change and wellbeing in an integrated manner.

Policy Influence and Scaling: The success of these living labs can influence policy at local, national, and international levels, potentially scaling their impact beyond their immediate

geographical areas to contribute to the global efforts against climate change and for human health and wellbeing.

In summary, the living labs in Israel and the Ocean Living Lab provide valuable frameworks for addressing the intertwined challenges of climate change and societal wellbeing, showcasing the potential of collaborative, innovative approaches for sustainable development.

TA evaluation

Alon Meiri's evaluation of the Transnational Access (TA) as part of the VITALISE project provides valuable insights into the program's effectiveness, strengths, and areas for improvement. Summary of the main aspects of Alon's evaluation:

Recommendations and Usefulness

Alon highly recommends the TA to colleagues or other researchers, indicating a very positive experience.

The Fast Track Training program included in the TA was found to be highly useful, with a rating of 8 out of 10.

Appreciated Aspects

Alon particularly appreciated the research tools provided, the accessibility of professionals, and the facilities offered from the beginning of the research activity.

Suggestions for Improvement

A suggestion was made to clarify from the start what is expected from the TA participants in terms of their research work.

Living Lab Collaboration

Alon rated various services provided by the hosting Living Lab highly, indicating a generally positive experience with the support and infrastructure offered.

Visited research infrastructures were the GAIA Ocean Living Lab and the Living Lab Smart Spaces, praised for their commitment to nature-based solutions, interdisciplinary approach, and citizen participation.

Weaknesses Noted

For improvement, Alon suggested the Ocean Living Lab could enhance citizen involvement and define the end-user more clearly.

VITALISE Products Usage

Alon found the VITALISE products such as the Data Tool and Panel Management tool helpful in understanding working models and methodologies for the TA research.

These products were rated in terms of user-friendliness and usefulness, indicating a positive impact on Alon's research work.

Future Needs

Alon expressed a need for increased collaboration with researchers and co-creators of the Living Labs in future research.

GAIA living lab involved staff focused on expert advice, mapping of stakeholders facilitating the co-creation sessions with other researchers. Total of hours: technical manager 120 hours and living lab manager 120 hours.

ID84 Analysis of the Role of Ecosystem-based Adaptation for Reducing Climate Risks and Improving Socioeconomic Wellbeing through a Study of Public Perceptions.

Study the role of Nature-based Solutions in improving community wellbeing and reducing climate vulnerability in the Basque Country, Spain.

Researcher: Ananya Tiwari (lead applicant),

Number of researchers: 1

Period: January 14th – February 15th 2024

Project summary

Background and objectives

This research study is based in the GAIA OcEAN living lab, located in the UNESCO-designated Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve in Basque, Spain. This study analyses the role of ecosystem-based climate adaptation strategies in reducing local coastal climate risks (such as erosion, coastal flooding, extreme weather events, sea level rise etc). Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve is a region filled with biodiversity, and home to 45,000 inhabitants, 80% of which are concentrated in the towns of Gernika and Bermeo.

The marshlands are critical for bird life, both as a nesting area and as a stopping or wintering site. The coastal wetlands are also a natural nursery of great importance for many marine species that spend their first years in this area. Besides its environmental wonders, Urdaibai features a cultural, architectural and archaeological heritage that is of high symbolic importance to the Basque people, such as Katillotxu and the Roman settlement of Forua. Gernika, made famous by the infamous bombing and Pablo Picasso's painting, is also located in the area.

Around 14% of the population makes a living out of the primary sector, mainly in farming, cattle-raising, forestry and fishing. The main expected impacts of climate change on this region include increased flooding and sea-level rise, reduction in annual precipitation, increased temperatures, and more. This will impact sectors like agriculture and forestry, as well as marine biodiversity.

The Climate Change Strategy of the Basque Country to 2050 states that the climate scenarios for Basque have broad horizons, specifically when it comes to climate adaptation. They present a level of uncertainty that can reduce gradually through more research. The report also highlights the need to generate local knowledge in Basque Country, by guiding lines of research in this regard, so that results can be obtained to facilitate decision-making. It also emphasises the need to mainstream climate action, to make communities less vulnerable to climate change, and the necessity of climate policy to bring all stakeholders of society onboard. It suggests institutional and stakeholder collaboration as necessities to address the cross-cutting nature of climate change. Finally, it states that effective climate adaptation strategies can also have co-benefits for socioeconomic well-being.

The GAIA OCEAN living lab provides a suitable platform to address all these interconnected issues. The quadruple helix model, part of the living lab structure, provides a platform for effective stakeholder engagement from different sections of society, including academia, public sector, industry and civil society. The infrastructure and research capacity available in the living lab can facilitate a study to analyse the current climate adaptation strategies as well as plan future ecosystem-based adaptation approaches in Urdaibai, Basque.

Since this living lab focuses on ecosystem services, biodiversity, green economy, and societal well-being, this study will explicitly analyse the role of ecosystem services in supporting climate

adaptation goals, as well as providing socioeconomic co-benefits to enhance overall community wellbeing.

The OCEAN living lab focuses on citizen-driven innovation for the ocean. This study will involve citizen and stakeholder engagement, to analyse the most effective coastal adaptation strategies in Basque to ensure community wellbeing, based in the living lab principles of co-creation and co-design.

This research will use the knowledge generated within the ongoing EU Horizon 2020 SCORE project and design a study to compare the ecosystem-based climate adaptation strategies in the SCORE Sligo Coastal City Living Lab and the VITALISE GAIA OCEAN living lab, thus encouraging knowledge-exchange and collaboration between the two EU projects.

Activities performed:

- Meetings and interviews with different stakeholders. More than 97 interviews executed during the TA.
- Co-creation sessions with researchers from Basque Country labs.
- Visiting spaces. Nature based solution of a river and coastal research institutions.
- Data collection from interviews and comparative research with project SCORE and Sligo region results.
- Presentation of TA result during the Vitalise final event (Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium).

Starting point of the comparative research

- The Basque Country has increasingly become more prone to climate risks such as storms, floods, heatwaves, droughts, erosion, and more.
- There is a lack of data on climate risks in the region, due to limited monitoring of climate hazards or hazard prevention strategies, which has affected the formulation of effective climate policies.
- Especially, there is limited data on the public perceptions of climate change risks, and how these risks affect vulnerable communities (such as elderly citizens, low-income groups, etc)
- Nature-based Solutions (NbS) can be an effective means to address climate risks, but there is no data on the role of NbS in reducing climate vulnerability and improving community wellbeing
- This study was conducted in collaboration with the EU SCORE project.

Figure 10. Coastal living labs. Challenges and integrated solutions.

Methodology and materials

- Interview and surveys with 90 participants.
- Recruitment was based on the living lab quadruple helix model. While most respondents were from academia and industry, there were some from public sector and civil society.
- Focus on climate-vulnerable communities or groups with knowledge/understanding of climate risks in the region

- Most responses were from Greater Bilbao Area, but there were also a lot of responses from coastal regions near Bilbao (Plentzia, Getxo, Sopela, etc) as well as the Urdaibai region and San Sebastian, making the survey comprehensive for the Basque region of Spain.

Some preliminary findings

	<p>People’s level of concern about climate change in the Basque Country, ranging between 1 to 5 (1 being lowest and 5 being highest). The highest number of people voted for 5 and 4, showing extremely high concern.</p>
	<p>People’s perceptions of impacts of climate change in their region, rated from lowest (1) to highest (5). The highest number of people voted for 3 or 4, showing medium to high impact.</p>
	<p>People’s perceptions on whether climate strategies/policies are effective enough in their region, rated from least effective (1) to highly effective (5). Almost 80% of people voted for 1 or 2, showing extremely ineffective policies in the region.</p>
	<p>People’s knowledge levels about NbS, ranging from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest). Most people voted for 3 or 4, showing medium to high level of knowledge about NbS.</p>

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Based on the information gathered from the VITALISE project's Transnational Access (TA) report and the post-TA evaluation questionnaire filled out by Ananya Tiwari, several conclusions and a future outlook can be drawn:

Conclusions

Stakeholder Engagement and Research Impact: The TA facilitated extensive engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders in the Basque Country, Spain, which was instrumental in gathering unique insights on public perceptions of climate change and the effectiveness of nature-based solutions. This engagement underpins the project's success in collecting valuable data that could influence climate planning and policy-making in the region.

Research Services Utilization: A variety of services provided by the living lab were crucial in conducting the research, such as networking, capacity building, expert opinion, and advisory services. These services facilitated the successful recruitment of stakeholders, organizing engagement activities, and collecting data, highlighting the importance of such infrastructural and methodological support in executing transnational research projects.

Preliminary Findings and Dissemination: The project yielded both qualitative and quantitative data that, despite needing further analysis, have already contributed to discussions at the VITALISE Health and Wellbeing Symposium. The intention to publish the results in academic journals, on the EU SCORE project website, and through policy briefs demonstrates a strong commitment to disseminating the findings to a broad audience, including stakeholders and policymakers.

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS): NBS offer innovative approaches to tackle climate change challenges, enhancing resilience and community well-being in the Basque Country. These solutions leverage the natural ecosystems' ability to mitigate climate change effects while promoting health and well-being.

Basque NBS Pilot: Impact on Well-being and Health: The Basque NBS pilot project focuses on assessing how nature-based solutions can significantly contribute to the local communities' well-being and health. Benefits include improved air quality, stress reduction, and promotion of healthy lifestyles.

Future of NBS: Engagement and Sustainability: To ensure the sustainability and long-term success of NBS, community engagement and the support of appropriate policies are crucial. This collaborative approach ensures that the solutions are not only effective but also align with the local community's needs and values.

Future Outlook

Continued Dissemination and Impact: With plans for widespread dissemination of research findings, there's potential for significant impact on climate adaptation strategies in the Basque

Country and beyond. The open access publication of data and policy briefs could foster broader engagement with and implementation of the research outcomes.

Potential for Commercialization: Opportunities to translate research findings into practical, marketable solutions for climate adaptation and stakeholder engagement are explored.

Sustainability of Stakeholder Engagement: The project's approach to stakeholder engagement offers a model for future research initiatives, emphasizing the importance of building strong relationships with local communities, academia, industry, and the public sector to tackle complex environmental challenges.

Enhancement of Research Infrastructures: Feedback from the TA experience, including the need for improved responsiveness, can inform the development of more efficient and responsive research infrastructures. This could enhance the support provided to future researchers, improving the effectiveness and impact of transnational access programs.

Overall, the VITALISE project's TA component has demonstrated the value of integrating diverse stakeholder perspectives into environmental research and the critical role of supporting services in facilitating successful research projects. The insights gained and the forthcoming dissemination efforts hold promise for informing climate adaptation efforts and fostering more resilient communities.

TA evaluation

Positive Feedback with Recommendations for Improvement: The feedback from Ananya Tiwari's post-TA evaluation was overwhelmingly positive, particularly appreciating the opportunity for deep engagement with local stakeholders and the cultural and contextual understanding gained.

GAIA living lab involved staff focused on expert advice, mapping of stakeholders facilitating the co-creation sessions with other researchers and the meeting with different stakeholders (more than 90 meetings were arranged). Different visits were organised to facilitate the activity of the TA (Bilbao, Plentzia, Getxo, Sopela, as well as the Urdaibai region and San Sebastian). During this visits the researcher was accompanied by GAIA living lab staff. Total of hours: technical manager 204 hours and living lab manager 284 hours.

2.7 INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab

INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab has completed a total of two (2) Transnational Access projects in the period from August to October 2023. A total of six (6) researchers visited the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab, one belonging to TA ID98, five belonging to TA ID92. From the TA studies performed in this specific INTRAS LL infrastructure, one abstract was submitted to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024.

Table 6. Status TA in INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab

Project	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
NLPElderly (ID98)	Aug-Sep. 23	Living lab project planning and management Expert opinion, and advisory services Idea selection and testing Prototyping test	9	32	1	Yes
EDAD.TECH (ID92)	Aug-Oct. 23	Living lab project planning and management Expert opinion, and advisory services Legal, regulation and safety standard support	44	27	5	Yes

		Capacity Building Idea selection and testing Co-creation session				
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ID98 NLPElderly. Exploration of natural language processing techniques for non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders in elderly people from home

Researcher: Andrea Johana Chaves (Colombia)

Participant Researchers: Alfonso Bahillo (supervisor) - Trascender Global S.A.S. (Colombia) - Collaboration with the University of Valladolid (Spain)

Number of researchers: 1

Period: Aug-Sep. 23

Project summary

Background, objectives and research activities

This study is dedicated to the exploration of natural language processing techniques for non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders in elderly people from home.

The project's central premise recognizes the profound impact of emotional states on individuals' interactions, self-care practices, health-related decision-making, and stress management capabilities. This influence is particularly pronounced in the elderly population, where age-related changes—such as chronic diseases, mobility independence loss, or the bereavement of close ones—pose significant risks to mental health, affecting their quality of life.

Considering the susceptibility of the elderly to mental health disorders due to these changes, NLPElderly aims to harness technological advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Digital Signal Processing (DSP) to provide effective support and interventions. These interventions are intended to maintain and enhance mental well-being in elderly populations, focusing on non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders from home.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the performed activities in the TA Research

Figure 11. Block diagram of the performed activities in the TA Research

The Transnational Access (TA) component of this research primarily concentrated on a preliminary study to establish a suitable methodology for constructing and preprocessing a dataset of unstructured information (opinion text). This dataset aims to glean insights into the emotional states or mental disorders of elderly individuals in domestic settings.

The project unfolded over a 41-day period, segmented into remote and in-person phases. The initial seven days (remote access) involved: Reviewing TA Planning with external researchers and determining data sources for dataset definition; Selecting an open-source dataset suitable for

application requirements, focusing on Spanish-language recordings in an indoor environment; Planning the preprocessing of the audio recordings dataset, followed by the development of the Speech-to-Text stage using OpenAI's WhisperIt for automatic speech recognition; Identifying speech patterns in the time and frequency domains to discern emotional states and reviewing these identified patterns. The subsequent 32 days (in-person TA) covered: Dataset Definition and Methodologies: Establishing dataset requirements and adapting methodologies from mental health professionals; Preprocessing of Audio Recordings: Utilizing WhisperIt for speech-to-text conversion and identifying speech patterns for emotional state recognition; NLP Methods and Performance Evaluation: Outlining potential NLP models for future emotion identification tasks. The final two days (remote access) focused on preparing the report with outcomes and findings and describing potential NLP models for future work.

Key achievements:

- Development of methodologies for mood identification.
- Creation of notebooks that facilitate the preprocessing of audio recordings and feature extraction for emotion recognition.
 - Notebook 1 for speech-to-text conversion. This notebook, created in Python within a Jupyter Notebook environment on Google Colab, facilitates Speech-to-Text conversion using Whisper models based on parameter count. It evaluates performance through Word Error Rate (WER) and visually compares the results.
 - Notebook 2 for audio pattern identification. This Python notebook facilitates audio preprocessing by first segmenting recordings based on silence. It then extracts temporal features like intensity and pitch and uses Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) for frequency domain analysis. Feature selection was guided by a review of current state-of-the-art methodologies.

The project harnessed expert opinions and advisory services from the Living Lab to navigate the complexities of mental health research. The involvement and insights of mental health professionals from the Living Lab was pivotal for the dataset construction, methodology selection, and ensuring ethical considerations in data collection from vulnerable populations.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The NLPElderly project has successfully laid the groundwork for employing NLP and DSP technologies to monitor mental health states in the elderly non-invasively. Through its initial stages, the project identified two methodologies for mood identification, developed tools for speech-to-text conversion, and identified speech patterns pertinent to emotional state recognition.

Moving forward, the project aims to explore and implement various NLP models, such as BERT and GPT, for identifying emotional states more accurately. Utilizing models like BERT, GPT, Word Embeddings, Emotion-specific Models, Contextual Embeddings, and Ensemble Models to improve emotion identification in text. The research's future scope involves refining these methodologies, expanding the dataset, and enhancing model performance to facilitate the broader application of these technologies in real-world settings.

Furthermore, the outcomes of this preliminary study are to be disseminated through technical reports and scientific publications, with the eventual goal of open sourcing the datasets for community use. This endeavour aligns with the project's commitment to advancing the field of mental health monitoring, particularly for vulnerable populations like the elderly.

The NLPElderly project not only contributes valuable insights into the intersection of technology and mental health but also opens avenues for future research and development that could significantly improve elderly care practices globally.

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, a Psychologist, a Neuropsychologist, an Administrative Manager, a Data Analyst, a Software Developer, and a Technical Expert. In total, approximately 76 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the NLPElderly research in the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab, for both remote and in-person Transnational Access. This is translated to around 10 working days.

The researcher highlighted her positive experience and satisfaction with the outcomes of the Transnational Access (TA) program, indicating that the TA output was higher than expected. The Fast Track Training Program was assessed as highly usefulness. The researcher particularly appreciated the opportunity to interact with ongoing projects relevant to her doctoral research and valued the guidance provided by INTRAS's LL Team, specially the INTRAS Neuropsychologist. This guidance was crucial for an adequate construction of the database. This points to the proactive and supportive approach of the INTRAS Living Lab (LL) team and the enriching opportunity to engage with their multidisciplinary research team. The assistance and transfer of research and Living Lab methodological expertise, particularly in understanding end-user needs and providing methodological support, were recognized for their high quality. It reflects a positive experience with room for minor improvements in technical support, aligning with the broader goal of engaging with real-world applications and extending the research's impact.

ID92 EDAD.TECH

Lead applicant: Lorena Paz (Argentina)

Participant researchers: Julieta Piñeiro (Argentina); Gonzalo Sierra (Argentina); Daniela Tamashiro; Cecilia Policastro (Argentina) - Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Buenos Aires (Argentina)

Number of researchers: 5

Period: Aug-Oct. 23

Project summary

Background and objectives

Background: The EDAD.TECH working group, with nearly two decades of experience, has focused on the crucial impact of the emotional dimension on older adults' interaction with Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). Through its ethnographic research, EDAD.TECH has sought to understand the complex relationship older adults have with technology, marked by ergonomic challenges, cybersecurity concerns, and a mix of fear and suspicion, leading to digital disengagement. This backdrop of challenges has underscored the need to mitigate and address effectively these barriers, promoting emotional empowerment and digital literacy among older adults to foster meaningful ICT use while enhancing well-being.

Objectives: This project aims to harness the innovative potential of Virtual Reality (VR) technologies and multisensory stimulation to improve the emotional well-being of older adults. Partnering with the INTRAS Foundation, the project considered as use case the SERENHE tele-rehabilitation platform that served as base to develop an innovative concept for integrating guided breathing exercises in

the system and evaluate its impact, acknowledging the benefits of such practices on well-being and the age-related decline.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The project employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research to capture the nuanced motivations and expectations of older adults regarding technology use.

It consisted in an iterative, user-centred design process, incorporating ethnographic design, co-creation sessions with end-users (Experts by Experience) during the in-person TA, and usability testing to evaluate and enhance the proposed technological solutions. This approach is underpinned by a strong theoretical framework grounded in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), User Experience (UX) design, and Design Thinking principles.

A hybrid TA work plan facilitated this research, combining remote access to the external researchers and in-person access to the Living Lab premises to the external lead researcher, to maximize collaborative efforts and stakeholder engagement and as an opportunity to learn from the Living Lab experiences once the group is considering establishing a Living Lab in Colombia.

Key activities include heuristic analysis of existing emotional well-being interventions, comprehensive usability testing, co-creation sessions to explore new features like rhythmic breathing methods, and the systematic documentation and reporting of findings to guide future development and implementation strategies.

With the support of the Living Lab, during the in-person Transnational Access (TA), the researchers engaged in several notable activities and dissemination actions, strengthening collaborations, and fostering partnerships among the external researchers respective entities in Colombia and research groups and different Spanish entities from Academia, Research, Creative, health and care sectors. Here's a highlight of these endeavours:

Week 1: Initial In-Person Activities

- Preparation of Wikitoki Event in Bilbao: planning of a collaborative session designed for individuals over 70 years old to engage with simple technological challenges and discuss digital technology design, accessibility, and ICT usage. This event was a joint effort between EDAD.Tech, Brand Creatiers, and Wikitoki, aiming to directly involve older adults in the conversation about technology and accessibility.

Week 2: Engagement with the SERENHE Project and Wikitoki Event in Bilbao (September 12, 2023)
[\[Link to the event\]](#)

Week 3: Demonstrations and Media Engagement

- Demo Sessions: Showcasing the SERENHE project tools in collaboration with the Living Lab team, integrating heuristic and UX ethnography studies to refine the project's approach.
- Media Engagement: A podcast interview with CADENA SER Radio Channel highlighted EDAD.tech's primary research, accompanied by an informational note prepared by the Living Lab, facilitating wider public engagement and awareness.

Week 4: User Interaction and Co-Creation Sessions

- VR Demonstrations: Conducting demonstrations in INTRAS's VR meditation room, focusing on immersive experiences for enhancing elder well-being.
- Co-Creation Session with Experts by Experience: This involved usability testing and user experience analysis from a well-being perspective, engaging 6 older adults in discussions for

potential feature enhancements and exploring the effectiveness of pranayama breathing in VR environments.

These activities underscore the commitment for engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders, from direct beneficiaries (older adults) to academic and professional communities, in understanding and leveraging VR for older adults' well-being. After the in-person TA, there was a compilation of expert input on VR, accessibility, and well-being to consolidate the collected insights.

The inclusive approach, combined with strategic dissemination and collaboration efforts, set a foundation for ongoing impact and future initiatives in the realm of technology-enhanced health and well-being for older populations. As future direction the researchers emphasize the broader dissemination of results (e.g. sharing outcomes at the Digital Equity Event and seminars at the Universidad de Buenos Aires), and continued work in innovative conceptual (e.g. for digital rhythmic breathing) solutions that can be incorporated in systems like the one offered by SERENHE tele-rehabilitation platform, supporting older adults in isolated, challenging environments or underserved regions.

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, a Psychologist, two Facilitators, an Administrative Manager, a Data Analyst, a Software Developer, and additional LL personnel, amounting to two more individuals. In total, approximately 114 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the EDAD.TECH research in the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab, for both remote and in-person Transnational Access. This is translated to around 15 working days.

Feedback from the evaluation questionnaire revealed that all visiting researchers found the TA's outcomes to meet or exceed their high expectations. The Fast Track Training Program was unanimously praised for its usefulness. Researchers appreciated the predisposition of the INTRAS LL team commenting the proactive approach of the INTRAS Living Lab (LL) team and the valuable opportunity to engage with the Group of Experts by Experience. The support provided, along with the transfer of research and Living Lab methodological expertise, especially in areas involving end users (such as co-creation and field testing), was recognized for its high quality.

A key strength of the INTRAS LL identified was its multidisciplinary research team. As an improving suggesting the desire for a space specifically designed for acoustics during co-creation and testing sessions. Despite facing last-minute changes to the agenda by the visiting researchers, which required adjustments in the logistics for the co-creation sessions, the LL team's swift and agile response ensured that the sessions could proceed on a different floor and rooms (not acoustic) without major issues.

Moreover, there was a unified acknowledgment of the potential and value in a follow-up action that offers the chance to remotely test prototypes and usage scenarios with older adults in Buenos Aires, Argentina. This consensus reflects a keen interest in extending the research's impact and underscores the practical benefits of engaging with real-world applications and environments.

2.8 LAUREA- Laurea Simulated Hospital

Table 7. Status TA in LAUREA simulated hospital

Project name	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA REMOTE	DAYS	TA PERSON	DAYS	Number of researchers	of Visit performed
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ID33	17.4.- 12.5.2023	Expert opinion, and advisory services; Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping; Legal, regulation and safety standard support	-	26	1	Yes
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ID33 Co-creation in Academia

Researcher: Matias Ignacio De La Calle/UNIBO

Number of researchers: 1

Period: 17.4.-12.5.2023

Project summary

Background and objectives

As a Health Research Development (RD) Manager at University of Bologna (UNIBO), the opportunity to access a Living Lab Research Infrastructure would allow the TA researcher to pursue the following objectives:

- To learn-by-doing the development and the implementation of Living Labs as a facilitator
- To apply the Living Lab approach in the home university for the development of research and innovation projects: from the scientific question to the ideation of sustainable impacts
- To propose Living Labs in European projects for the co-creation of innovative solutions and societal impacts with a wide multi-stakeholder participation
- To transfer Living Lab approach to all the Research Development Units within his University Research Services Division (ARIC)

Research activities

The TA researcher conducted direct participant observation and semi-structured interviews during his visit in Laurea Simulated Hospital.

Direct Participant Observation

The researcher observed two activities: New Service Development and Innovative Business Models lectures/group discussions (observing teaching/student presentations) and implementation of Laurea's Learning by Developing pedagogical model. Furthermore, he participated in a field trip and observed Living Lab "Robota Project" experts and end users with mental and physical impairment interactions. Overall, the observed activities involved more than 50 participants.

Semi-structured interviews (qualitative)

The TA researcher interviewed Laurea's Living Lab experts (n=28) from various fields. Experts included project managers, lecturers, experts by experience and pedagogical managers.

Results and conclusions

Increased knowledge of Living Lab methodology will be integrated into current EU project proposals within Horizon Europe Cluster 1 Health and Mission Cancer. The network of Living Lab experts and infrastructures in Europe will be enriched.

In the long term, the following impacts are anticipated:

- On average, nine proposals are submitted per Call in Horizon Europe Cluster 1 Health and Mission Cancer (with two Calls published annually). Among them, UNIBO (coordinates between three and four projects per year, totalling approximately six projects annually). All of these projects are expected to be funded by the European Commission, aiming to maximize societal impact through innovative participatory approaches. The TA researcher's enhanced knowledge and expertise will significantly leverage Living Labs, enabling him and his collaborators to transfer the approach into EU R&I projects coordinated by UNIBO.
- Promotion of Living Labs in EU research and innovation projects in the Health and Wellbeing domain, fostering co-creation and open innovation among the main actors of the Quadruple Helix Model by adhering to ENoLL principles.
- Increased involvement of Living Lab methods and experts in EU projects.

2.9 McGill-CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab

While McGill accepted five TA projects, due to factors out of our control, two of these (ID14 and ID48) had to cancel prior to beginning. This section presents the three TA projects that were held at the McGill-CRIR LL between June 2023 and March 2024. From the TA studies performed in this specific INTRAS LL infrastructure, one abstract was submitted to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February 2024.

Table 8. Status TA in McGill-CRIR Rehabilitation living lab

Project name	TA period	TA SERVICES	TA DAYS REMOTE	TA DAYS PERSON	Number of researchers	of Visit performed
ID22 & 44	June 21 - July 21, 2023 (ID22) & June 21- Aug 3, 2023 (ID44)	Expert opinion, Equipment and facility rental service advisory services; Living lab project planning and management; Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	NV: 21 LMK: 19	NV: 18 LMK: 20	2	yes
ID29	Sept 1- 30, 2023	Expert opinion, advisory services; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Marketing and sales support	11	30	1	yes
ID25	Feb 17 - March 7, 2024	Capacity building; Innovation network ¹⁴ orchestration; Expert opinion, and advisory services; Living lab project planning and management	CM: 14 GR: 11	CM:13	2	yes
ID14	cancelled					
ID48	cancelled					

ID22 & ID44 A Day at the Museum: Using Audio-Guided Visual Search to Increase Engagement Among Older Adults Visiting Art Museums.

Researcher: Naomi Vingron (lead researcher) and Lea Müller Karoza. Goethe University, Germany.

Number of researchers: 2

Period: June 21 - July 21, 2023 (ID22) & June 21-Aug 3, 2023 (ID44)

Project summary

Background and objectives

Older adults' mental and physical health benefits from engagement in stimulating activities. However, seeking out activities which stimulate people of advanced age on social, creative and educational levels is not always easy. The study investigated ways to make museums more accessible for older adults by changing the conventionally used audio guides to ones including *gamified* visual search tasks. These describe the artworks in simple language which guide the listeners through the paintings, encouraging them to search for regions and objects. Since adapted audio guides might also be beneficial for younger adults, as they allow viewers to discover details about the presented artworks that might otherwise not be attended to, thereby increasing engagement the study also included young adults.

While the original plan was to collect data on-site in the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts (MMFA), this was not possible due to circumstances at the museum that were out of our control. Instead, the TA researchers created an experiment, in partnership with researchers in Montreal, in which participants viewed images painting on a computer screen while listening to an audio guide and had their eye movements recorded. The experiment was conducted in a laboratory using an eye tracking device (desk-mounted EyeLink 1000 from SR Research).

The audio guides participants heard referred to areas of the painting they were viewing. The relevant areas of the painting were marked as regions of interest. As well, the time point when these items are mentioned in the audio description was cross-referenced with the eye movements recorded to assess whether participants look at the areas being described. Subsequently, participants were asked three content recall and one visual recall question. Specifically, content recall questions pertained to information mentioned in the audio guide and visual recall questions consisted of two sections of paintings (i.e., one from the painting that was just presented and another from a painting by the same artist) and asked participants to determine which of the sections was part of the previously seen painting. The recall questions were presented on the screen after each painting.

During the TA in Montreal, the TA researchers tested 9 older and 4 younger adult participants. Upon their return to Frankfurt, an additional 13 young adults were also tested.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

While results of the studies are still being analysed, preliminary results show that the use of audio guides, specifically the gamification through linguistically guided visual attention, appears to increase meaningful engagement with art: listening to an audio guide was associated with increased fixations to an area of interest in the painting while it was being described in the audio guide.

Figure 12. comparative result regarding the use of audio guides

However, this did not necessarily translate to an increase in feelings of engagement. Future directions include using portable eye tracking technologies to extend this research to museum settings, capitalize on gamification through linguistically guided visual attention, and working with museums to create more engaging audio guides to motivate older adults and those with impairments to visit museums.

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support was also provided by a technical manager and a Data analyst. In total, approximately 237 hours were spent by the professionals mentioned above to support the realization of the Day at the Museum study in the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab, for both remote and in-person Transnational Access. This translates to approximately 30 working days.

The two researchers shared their positive experience and satisfaction with the outcomes of the Transnational Access (TA) program, despite changes that had to be made to the protocol. They indicated that the TA output was higher than expected and shared that The Fast Track Training Program was as highly useful. In particular, the researchers stated that they appreciated the opportunity to have access to a participant pool that is difficult for them to recruit at their home university and valued the guidance provided by McGill-UdeM-CRIR LL Team. In addition, they appreciated the research connection that were shared by the LL that permitted them to collect data in a specialised eye-tracking laboratory when it became clear that the research would not be allowed to be held on-site at the MMFA as had originally been planned.

ID29 Privacy and Data Protection Challenges Affecting Internet of Things for Mental Health: Comparative Perspectives and Pathways for Soft Regulation in Europe and Canada

Researcher: Elisabeth Steindl. University of Vienna, Austria

Number of researchers: 1

Period: Sept 1- 30, 2023

Project summary

Background and objectives

The COVID-19 public health crisis increased the uptake of e-mental health services, particularly by use of telemedicine and mental health apps (OECD, 2021). In general, e-mental health services may serve various purposes (e.g. information sharing, digital therapies, patient monitoring) and use domains (e.g. patients, providers, educational institutions, private sector actors). This project focused on Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled mental health services that are underpinned by pervasive and ubiquitous computing. These new enabling technologies have great potential for improving mental health diagnoses, treatment and care due to their ability to collect real-time data measuring the activity and behavioural patterns of people.

Despite their potential health-related benefits, there is a lack of trust in digital health services due to risks for privacy and data protection (European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, 2018). Against this background, this project aimed to analyse whether soft law instruments can address privacy and data protection challenges that are specific to the deployment of IoT devices for mental health. By collaborating with two Living Labs (the AUTH Living Environment Simulation and the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab) in two different jurisdictions (EU and Canada), the two TA researchers (Richard Rak and Elisabeth Steindl) aimed to provide a comparative account of regulatory deficiencies and explore whether and which soft law instruments could facilitate good practices in e-mental health. Dr. Steindl conducted semi-structured interviews with selected individuals from the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab and experts associated with the Living Lab and its research staff.

These interviews permitted the gathering of information about the practical experiences of experts, focusing on how they address legal, ethical, and technological challenges related to privacy and data protection. Information about the interviewees' experiences with compliance in light of the current or upcoming regulatory framework was also collected. Beyond these topics, the interviewees were also asked for their perspectives on whether soft law instruments, such as standards, codes of conduct, and certification mechanisms, could serve as effective measures to complement and enhance the safeguarding of privacy and personal data for individuals (data subjects, patients). The project allowed Dr Steindl to establish contacts with the Mental Health Commission of Canada to gain insights into ongoing policy considerations concerning e-mental health in Canada, which harmoniously complemented and completed the findings of the interviews conducted with experts from the LL.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

The interviews at the LL explored a wide array of challenges pertaining to privacy and data protection in the implementation and utilization of digital technologies for mental health, as well as the future impact of AI on mental health, navigating the space between innovation and regulation. By leveraging the strengths of each jurisdiction and adopting a holistic approach, the project sought to ensure the responsible and ethical deployment of digital technologies for mental health. Canada's soft law approach to e-mental health, with a National Assessment Framework for e-mental health apps, holds potential lessons for the EU context. In the planning stages, there is an initiative for a

Certification Scheme and incentives, such as the National Library for e-mental health apps. Moreover, the development of a Canadian e-mental health strategy and ongoing policy considerations for AI in e-Mental Health bear potential for the upcoming EU mental health strategy.

A short description can be found in a blogpost about the project published on the Website of the Department of Innovation and Digitalisation in Law, University of Vienna: [Transatlantic Insights into Digital Technologies for Mental Health \(univie.ac.at\)](https://www.univie.ac.at/transatlantic-insights-into-digital-technologies-for-mental-health).

TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). A Technical manager and administrative manager also provided support. In total, approximately 85 hours were spent by all the professionals mentioned above to support the realization of the Privacy and Data Protection Challenges research carried out at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab, for both remote and in-person Transnational Access. This translates to approximately 11 working days.

The researcher shared their positive experience and satisfaction with the outcomes of the Transnational Access (TA) programme. They shared that the TA output was higher than expected. Professor Steindl particularly appreciated engaging in a thought-provoking mini symposium with representatives from the Mental Health Commission of Canada (MHCC) in Ottawa, an opportunity that was put in place through the McGill-UdeM-CRIR LL Team. In her own words: “This exchange added valuable perspectives and enriched the comprehension of the hurdles and the potential inherent in the field of e-mental health in Canada.”

ID25 Identification of language problems in Parkinson Disease

Researcher: Christina Manouilidou (lead researcher) and Georgia Roumpea, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

Number of researchers: 2

Period: Sept 1- 30, 2023

Project summary

Background and objectives

Apart from the obvious dysarthric impairments which are due to impaired motor functions, Parkinson disease (PD) patients are known to have difficulties in various language domains, affecting both grammar and vocabulary, as well as supra-linguistic elements, such as prosody. Specifically, they have difficulties with both comprehension and production of complex sentences resulting in the production of simpler but grammatically correct sentences. When it comes to vocabulary, processing of action words is impaired as well as comprehension of emotion words. Both linguistic and emotional prosody as well as emotional connotations of words and sentences, especially negative ones have been found impaired. Finally, speech in PD is less expressive and monotonous and is characterized by inappropriate pauses between words. The study aims at exploring two of these aspects of language impairments in PD and more specifically vocabulary and complex sentence comprehension through a picture naming task and a sentence-picture matching task. This project was embedded within a larger project investigating the effects of exercise on PD that was already underway at the LL. The two tasks described below were developed and added to the protocol to investigate language changes in this population.

Picture naming task

- a. Participants were asked to name various pictures depicting four categories of words: 1) common nouns, e.g. a *chair* (n = 20); 2) common verbs, e.g. *to read* (n = 20); 3) deverbial processes, e.g. *cooking* (n = 20); 4) deverbial agents, i.e. people who perform activities, e.g. *singer* (n = 20). The task was computer-based with each word category presented as a separate block. Participants did not have any time limit to provide their answers, which were manually recorded by the experimenter.

Sentence-picture matching task

The sentences represented complex structures, such as:

1. Centre-embedded relative clauses (CE), e.g. *The girl who is combing the mom is holding a mirror.*
2. Right-branching relative clauses (RB), e.g. *The girl is combing the mom who is holding a mirror.*
3. Object Verb Subject sentences (OVS), e.g. *It is the mom who the girl is combing.*

The task was also computer-based. Sentences appeared randomly at the top of the screen with three pictures, and the participants had to match each sentence with the correct picture. Participants did not have any time limit to provide their answers, which were manually recorded by the experimenter.

In collaboration with the McGill-UdeM-CRIR LL technical manager and a researcher with expertise in PD, the first part of the onsite TA visit was dedicated to finalizing the experimental materials, finalizing the experimental task and pilot testing with native speakers of English. This was done concurrently with literatures performed by the TA student remotely. This was followed by training of a research assistant to help with participant recruitment and testing and the preparation of the tasks in French. Four (n=4) PD patients were tested during the TA visit. Data collection will be continuing until summer 2024.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Preliminary data analysis is ongoing and preliminary results are presented below.

Picture naming task

Accuracy

Figure 13. Accuracy rates (%) for the different types of words in the Picture naming task

Sentence-picture matching task

Accuracy

Figure 14. Accuracy rates (%) for the different types of sentences in the Sentence-picture matching task

Reaction Times

Figure 15. Mean Reaction time (milliseconds) for the different types of sentences in the Sentence-picture matching task

Given that the TA visit was conducted in February 2024 and that data collection is ongoing, there are no current conclusions to present at the moment. However, it is anticipated that results of these tasks will help provide a more detailed picture of the specific areas of language that are affected in PD. This in turn can lead to more focused language interventions for this population.

TA evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). A Technical manager and a research assistant also provided support. In total, approximately 161 hours were spent by all the professionals mentioned above to support the realization of the study while it was carried out at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab, for both remote and in-person Transnational Access. This translates to approximately 20 working days.

Access to the McGill-UdeM-CRIR LL provided the TA researchers to have access to a population of patients (PD) that would not be possible to obtain at their home university. Additionally, the TA visit permitted her access to experts working with populations with language disorders (Eva Kehayia) and

experts working with Parkinson's disease patients (Marc Roig) who helped formulate the final versions of the tasks for the study.

3 Discussion

The following section describe the services offered by the living labs during the TA.

3.1 AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab

3 researchers from 2 organizations visited the AUTH Human Centrifuge and Rehabilitation Living Lab within a course of 7 months (July 2023-February 2024). 2 of these researchers came through the Science and Research Centre Koper, Slovenia (ID23) and the other from Rasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam, Netherlands (ID95).

The study of examining neuromuscular adaptation in stroke patients dur to different G-loads (ID23) lasted for two weeks, while the study for the investigation of benefits of centrifugation on lymphedema (ID95) was supposed to last 2 months. In both studies, the AUTH staff was highly engaged, assisting researchers in all steps of the process, from the application to the ethics committee, protocol design, participants enrolment and collection of data.

More specifically, for the study with ID23, no ethical application needed to be submitted since the researchers utilized part of the protocol originally designed for the JRA1 study. One participant visited the lab in advance of the data collection, to design together with the AUTH team the protocol and test the infrastructure. At that point, researchers from our team spent many hours daily with the external researcher, assisting him with every part of the process, even performing test data collection to ensure optimal coordination of all provided services. Upon the second visit of the Slovenian team, when the actual data collection took place, AUTH team identified possible participants in advance, to facilitate immediate data collection, once the external researchers were here. Even after their arrival, one local researcher was always accompanying the external ones to the centrifuge, to assist with data collection, since one member of the Slovenian team could not attend the visit due to medical reasons. Additionally, the SAHC operator and dedicated doctor were always at the premises.

For the study with ID95, an ethical committee application needed to be prepared in advance to the visitation. The experts from the AUTH team assisted the researchers every step of the preparation process, offering useful insights on the pipeline. Even when he first application was rejected and needed to be resubmitted, the AUTH team played a crucial in the preparation of the second application. While the external researcher waited for the approval, the internal ones provided their knowledge with data analysis, helping her prepare for the analysis process following the data collection. Additionally, the AUTH team assisted with the familiarization with the infrastructure. A first participant identification was performed from the internal researchers, although due to the ethics application being rejected a second time, the data collection never took place.

To summarize, the following services were used by each visiting team:

- ID23: **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services:** Providing expert insights and advice to guide the research and application of nature-based solutions, **Methodological Support and Guidance:** Assisting with the design and implementation of research methodologies. **Data collection and analysis:** Discussing data analysis methodologies and assisting during the data collection phase. **Equipment rental:** the visiting researchers used only the LL equipment under the supervision of the AUTH team. **Stakeholders' engagement:** Helping with participants identification and onboarding.
- ID95: **Legal Regulation and Safety Standard Support:** Offering guidance on compliance with legal and safety standards relevant to the research and interventions and helping them

with the ethical committee applications. **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services:** Providing expert insights and advice to guide the research and application of nature-based solution. **Methodological Support and Guidance:** Assisting with the design and implementation of research methodologies. **Stakeholders' engagement:** Helping with participants identification.

3.2 GAIA- Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation.

Both ID69 and ID84 at the GAIA Ocean Living Lab illustrate the effective use of living lab services to bridge scientific research and community engagement. The expert advisory, stakeholder integration, and project management services provided a solid foundation for both projects, enabling them to address complex environmental and social issues through innovative, inclusive, and culturally sensitive approaches. The co-creation sessions, in particular, highlighted the labs' commitment to participatory research, ensuring that the outcomes are relevant, sustainable, and have a real impact on the community's well-being and resilience.

The TAs demonstrate how living labs can serve as catalysts for innovation and change, fostering sustainable development and enhancing community well-being through inclusive and collaborative approaches.

ID69: Performing Arts-Smart Space

Description: Conducted from March 2-11, 2024, this project, led by Alon Meiri from Israel, focused on creating a performing arts space in public settings to explore the relationship between population well-being, climate change, and the use of public spaces. The project collaborated closely with the Gernika-Lumo municipality and involved entities like Gernika Gogoratuz, a Research Centre for Peace.

The project successfully drew parallels between innovative community practices in Israel and the Ocean Living Lab, focusing on enhancing well-being through cultural activities. It underscored the importance of integrating artistic endeavors with climate resilience efforts, enriching the community's cultural and environmental landscape.

Services Used:

- **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services:** Alon Meiri utilized expert advice to integrate performing arts effectively within public spaces aimed at enhancing communal well-being. This service provided critical insights into designing spaces that are both functional and culturally enriching.
- **Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping:** This service was vital in identifying and engaging community leaders, local government, and organizations like Gernika Gogoratuz. It facilitated an understanding of the community's needs and expectations, ensuring that the project aligned well with local cultural and social dynamics.
- **Project Planning and Management:** Managed the logistics and timeline of the project, ensuring that all activities from workshops to public engagements were executed smoothly. This service ensured that resources were optimally utilized and that the project adhered to its planned schedule.
- **Co-Creation Sessions:** Engaged a wide range of participants, including community members and local artists, to collaboratively design the performing arts space. This approach fostered a sense of ownership and relevance among the stakeholders, making the initiative more sustainable and rooted in the community's fabric.

ID84: Ecosystem-based Adaptation for Reducing Climate Risks

Description: Spanning from January 14 to February 15, 2024, this research, led by Ananya Tiwari, studied the effectiveness of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in improving community well-being and reducing climate vulnerability in the Basque Country, Spain. The study was based in the UNESCO-designated Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve, a region noted for its rich biodiversity and cultural significance.

This project highlighted the critical role of NbS in enhancing community resilience to climate impacts, emphasizing the importance of local stakeholder engagement in developing effective adaptation strategies. The research findings are poised to contribute significantly to local and regional climate policy, advocating for integrated, community-focused approaches to climate change.

Services Used:

- **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services:** Ananya Tiwari leveraged expert advice to understand and implement ecosystem-based strategies effectively. This included insights into managing coastal and environmental risks and integrating these strategies within the local socio-economic context.
- **Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping:** Critical in engaging a diverse range of stakeholders from various sectors. This service helped in identifying key players whose input was crucial for the comprehensive understanding and implementation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS). Conducted over 97 interviews with stakeholders to gather diverse perspectives on climate risks and adaptation strategies.
- **Project Planning and Management:** This service was integral to orchestrating the numerous activities ranging from interviews to data analysis, ensuring that each phase of the project was aligned with the overall objectives and completed within the allocated timeframe.
- **Co-Creation Sessions:** These sessions involved local stakeholders in the design and refinement of climate adaptation strategies, ensuring that the solutions were not only scientifically sound but also culturally and socially acceptable. This participatory approach helped in tailoring the strategies to meet specific local needs.
- **Methodological Support and Guidance:** Assisting with the design and implementation of research methodologies. Comparative analysis of activities in Basque Country and previous research developed by researchers in their countries. Comparative analysis with the SCORE project in Sligo, focusing on similar climate adaptation initiatives. Presentation of research findings at the VITALISE final event, aiming to influence broader policy and practice.

3.3 THOMAS MORE Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care

Four researchers from two different institutions applied to conduct their research in the Thomas More Motion lab research infrastructure (ID43 & ID57). Participants for the study with the (peri)menopausal women were recruited from LiCalab's panel (ID57), whereas for the Dynaback testing Thomas More staff reach out to companies where physical work was performed to run the study after prototype testing with internal staff (ID43).

Although the study about Physical activity and menopause (ID43) lasted for little over three months, the time spent by our staff during the remote data collection was limited to 8 hours. This comprises the time needed to answer questions through email or calls with individuals that needed help, as well as a short check halfway the study to see whether all was going according to plan. Participants got a roadmap that was prepared in advance, containing for instance a manual on how to use the Withings watch, in order to solve most commonly occurring problems. Ethical approval for this study was obtained by the visiting researcher in Ireland. All practical requirements for the Vitalise project

were fulfilled immediately when asked because of the smooth communication with these researchers. The results from the current study will act as input for follow up research, which aims to develop a digital physical activity intervention for middle-aged, menopausal women. This will have a range of impacts, across the short to long term, in areas of national and global health and wellbeing policy. Although menopause is a normal ageing process, the hormonal changes in this period of life may lead to many physical, physiological and social changes, resulting in deteriorations in quality of life. Increasing physical activity in this cohort may decrease menopausal symptoms and improve quality of life. Empowering middle-aged women to take responsibility for their health and wellbeing by becoming more physically active, may also reduce their risk and/or prevent the onset of a number of chronic health conditions such as coronary heart disease. This research has therefore the potential to make a significant long-term impact on population health if adopted.

For the Dynawork study (ID43), ethical approval was obtained by Thomas More Mobilab&Care colleagues. During the visits, a lot of work was done in a very efficient way. However, we experienced some difficulties in communication and planning for this project. The second visit was postponed from August to October due to last minute changes of plans of the visiting researcher. The third visit was postponed up to three times even after meetings with external stakeholders had been scheduled. Additionally, several reminders were needed for the lead applicant in order to comply with all practical TA requirements and agreed deadlines were often violated. Nevertheless, the research in this project is considered to be valuable as the smart Dynaback shirt now generates more reliable data after calibration with validated measurements from the Thomas More Motion lab research infrastructure. Using the Dynaback shirt with integrated sensors, ergonomics can be assessed easily and automatically in a physical working environment. This way, the smart shirt contributes to eliminating risk factors and injuries on the work floor.

In the paragraphs below, an overview can be found of the different services that were used for the Thomas more Motion lab research projects.

Services used for ID43: Living lab project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Intake and matching, panel management; Equipment and facility rental service; Expert opinion, and advisory services; Prototyping test; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.

Algorithms of the Dynaback shirt have been optimised after comparison with validated Captive motion measurements of the Thomas More Motion lab. The expertise of our engineers was of great importance for the operationalisation of this process. Dynaback shirts were worn by Thomas More colleagues to do some prototype testing. After a few improvements, the shirt was used in a small-scale real-life study involving 17 factory employees performing physical work.

Services used for ID57: LL project planning and management; Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Intake and matching; panel management; concept and proof-of-concept test/concepts feasibility study; and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation.

Oonagh and Thomas More staff have written the protocol together to make sure all measurements were feasible in the RI. Physical activity testing was conducted in the Thomas more Motion lab. After this two-hour session, the ten participants wore a smart watch that monitored their real-life activity over a 3 month period. The LiCalab panel manager that had recruited the participants through LiCalab's panel was available in case any question arose during these home monitoring phase.

3.4 INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab

Between August and October 2023, INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab two TA projects, NLPElderly (ID98) and EDAD.TECH (ID92), were executed, engaging a total of six researchers and submitting an abstract to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium.

NLPElderly (ID98), led by Andrea Johana Chaves from Trascender Global S.A.S. (Colombia), with Alfonso Bahillo supervising from the University of Valladolid (Spain), embarked on a mission to harness Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Digital Signal Processing (DSP) technologies. Their goal was to develop non-invasive methods for monitoring mental disorders in elderly individuals directly from their homes. This 41-day project, incorporating both remote and in-person phases, focused on the meticulous construction and preprocessing of a dataset to analyze emotional states or mental disorders of the elderly. The team's innovative approach resulted in the development of Python notebooks for speech-to-text conversion and audio pattern identification, setting a new benchmark for mood identification methodologies. **Services used for ID98:** This project made extensive use of expert opinion and advisory services, which were instrumental in navigating the complexities of mental health research and ensuring ethical considerations in data collection. The living lab project planning and management service provided a structured framework for executing the project efficiently, from dataset definition to methodology adaptation. Additionally, the prototyping test and idea selection and testing services enabled the NLPElderly team to iteratively refine their approach, resulting in the development of innovative tools for mood identification through speech analysis.

EDAD.TECH (ID92), led by Lorena Paz from the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Buenos Aires (Argentina), tackled the emotional barriers older adults face with technology. With a deep-rooted background in ethnographic research, the EDAD.TECH team aimed to enhance emotional well-being through Virtual Reality (VR) and multisensory stimulation, employing the SERENHE tele-rehabilitation platform as a base for their innovative concept. This project unfolded over a span of 71 days accumulated among the five participating researchers, blending remote for four of the researchers and mixed, with an important in-person stay by Lorena, involving research activities to foster user-centered design and co-creation sessions. Their efforts culminated in interactive events and demonstrations that not only engaged the elderly in the technological conversation but also paved the way for future advancements in elder care and digital literacy. **Services used for ID92:** engaged with a broader spectrum of services to address the emotional barriers older adults face with technology. Co-creation sessions and usability testing were at the heart of this project, fostering direct engagement with end-users and enabling the consultations around the power of VR-based interventions tailored to the needs and preferences of older adults, and set the scene for a new module introducing mindful breathing techniques such as pranayama to complement VR scenarios and tools for supporting older adults wellbeing while also supporting the acceptance of new technologies and complementary rehabilitation tools for more innovative programs. The project also benefited from legal, regulation, and safety standard support, ensuring compliance across different jurisdictions and safeguarding participant welfare. Capacity building services enhanced the team's expertise in VR and multisensory stimulation, while living lab project planning and management ensured a seamless integration of activities, from ethnographic research to start prototype configuration.

The execution of both projects within the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab environment was underpinned by a comprehensive range of services, including living lab project planning and management, expert opinion and advisory services, and co-creation sessions, among others. This

supportive framework was instrumental in facilitating the research activities, from idea selection and testing to prototyping and usability testing.

These projects facilitated international collaborations, paving the way for a future Pan-European ecosystem that connects living labs and social sciences, extending beyond rehabilitation and elderly care to person-centered work. The coverage of travel expenses for researchers from Colombia and Argentina was crucial for enhancing the research process and fostering close collaboration with lead researchers. These efforts yielded valuable lessons on international collaboration, service utilization, and their impact on participants and the broader community.

The projects highlighted INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab's role as an innovation catalyst, offering researchers a supportive ecosystem (innovation and rehabilitation) to test new technologies and methodologies. Identified areas for improvement include refining infrastructure for specific research activities and providing more technical support for programming, which were not initially part of the TA objectives. Addressing these challenges involves optimizing lab spaces for varied methodologies and better managing expectations.

Challenges encountered, particularly with Lorena, necessitated assertive management, including issues with expense reporting and unexpected changes to the TA plan. These challenges demanded significant administrative effort to maintain research integrity and adhere to policies, despite increasing the complexity of the process. The Living Lab team's commitment to ethical and responsible research practices was paramount, especially in interactions with participants, ensuring their meaningful involvement.

3.5 LAUREA- Laurea Simulated Hospital

One researcher from the University of Bologna (ID33) visited Laurea Simulated Hospital in April-May 2023. The TA researcher conducted direct participant observation and semi-structured interviews during his visit to gain the following objectives: to learn-by-doing the development and the implementation of Living Labs as a facilitator; to apply the Living Lab approach in the home university for the development of research and innovation projects; to propose Living Labs in European projects for the co-creation of innovative solutions and societal impacts with a wide multi-stakeholder participation; and to transfer Living Lab approach to all the research development units within his University .

Several services were used during the TA. Expert opinions and advisory services were essential throughout the process to give the researcher a realistic idea of the research potentials during the TA visit. Laurea has very multidisciplinary and cross-sectoral Living Lab activities, so mapping and familiarizing the researcher with them was an essential service during and prior the TA and in preparation for it. The TA researcher was also supported in planning his research and in administrative matters related to the visit, such as reporting and drafting the required documents.

Due to the nature of the research, no ethical review was needed from the Ethics Committee. However, any research involving Laurea's personnel requires obtaining a research permit from Laurea. Thus, the researcher was supported in applying for a research permit by familiarizing him with Laurea's instructions regarding the research permit, by reviewing the research protocol and by revising research permit application. Stakeholder analysis and mapping was a very central service in TA. Identifying suitable participants from Laurea's five higher education units and six physical campuses was essential to the success of the study. Recruitment of participants required considerable effort from the Living Lab personnel as well.

To summarize, the following services were used during the TA:

- **Expert opinion, and advisory services:** Providing expert opinions, guidance and advice at all stages of the research process.
- **Living lab project planning and management:** Project planning along with the external researcher prior and during the TA
- **Legal, regulation and safety standard support:** Reviewing research protocol, and preparing and revising research permit application.
- **Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping:** Identifying and recruiting potential research participants. Facilitating the access to different type of stakeholders for interviews.

3.6 McGill- CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab

Between June 2023 and March 2024, the CRIR-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab helped support three TA projects, with one of these (ID 22-44) having an abstract submitted to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium. In total five researchers from three different projects performed TA activities at the either in person, remotely or in a hybrid manner. Of these, three were researchers and two were graduate students from three institutions from different countries (Austria, Germany and Slovenia). The projects were all quite different but what they had in common was that our living lab had access to equipment, expertise, and populations of interest that were not readily available to them at their respective host institutions. For example, project ID25 required us to contact and recruit a population of interest (individuals with Parkinson's disease). This was possible for us to do since there are currently projects ongoing on-site with this population.

For the two projects that required ethics approval (ID22-44 and ID25) ethical approval was coordinated and obtained with help from the LL team prior to the visit. While they were ultimately obtained, the work involved was quite time consuming as we had to act as the go-betweens between the local committee and the researchers. For the visit that did not require ethics approval (ID 29), there was lots of preparation that was required prior to the visit to help identify the most appropriate people for interviews and set up introductions between them and the lead researcher. Another unforeseen difficulty involved the administrative paperwork that was required by McGill University. Figuring out what was required by them and who to contact was challenging at times. Furthermore, the reimbursement of the stays took much longer to process by the university than we had expected, since they were not familiar with these types of research visits and the expense reports we submitted were returned to us multiple times with questions and requests for additional supporting receipts. However, having a signed TA agreement did help resolve some of these issues more quickly. The relatively short time span in which the researchers could perform their visit (less than one year from the time they received their acceptance) also almost caused one project to need to be cancelled (ID25). However, in the end the researcher did come for the onsite part of the project, albeit almost at the very end of the grant. This gave them very little time to submit their final report and other information we required to write our end of grant reports.

Considering the evaluations reports and feedback from researchers, the services used from the McGill-UdeM-CRIR living lab include the following.

For all projects

- **Expert Opinion and Advisory Services:** Providing expert insights and advice to guide the research.
- **Living lab project planning and management:** Project planning along with the external researcher prior and during the TA
- **Living lab project management:** management of resources, time and budget throughout the pilot execution phase

For projects ID22-44 and ID25:

- **Methodological Support and Guidance:** Assisting with the design and implementation of research methodologies.
- **Data collection and analysis:** Discussing data analysis methodologies and assisting during the data collection phase.

- **Equipment rental:** the visiting researchers used only the LL equipment under the supervision of the McGill-UdeM-CRIR team.
- **Legal Regulation and Safety Standard Support:** Offering guidance on compliance with legal and safety standards relevant to the research and interventions and helping them with the ethical committee applications.
- **Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping:** Identifying and recruiting potential research participants. Facilitating the access to different type of stakeholders for interviews.
 - For project ID22-44
- **Dissemination:** presentation of the outcomes in VITALISE final event – Health & Wellbeing Living Lab summit

4 Conclusion

This document presents an overview about the performed TA activities of six research infrastructures that participate in this work package, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation, advance knowledge in the field of rehabilitation and highlight its critical role.

Considering the information and the comprehensive analysis presented in this report, we can conclude that the VITALISE project has successfully demonstrated the significance and impact of Transnational Access (TA) across different research infrastructures in the domain of health and wellbeing. The project engaged a wide range of research infrastructures across various regions, each bringing unique contributions and insights to the overarching goals of the VITALISE project.

Comparative Analysis and Conclusions

Diverse Research Infrastructures: The report showcases the breadth of research infrastructures involved, each focusing on different aspects of health, wellbeing, and rehabilitation. This diversity underscores the project's comprehensive approach to addressing various health-related challenges through innovative research and collaboration.

Innovative Projects and Outcomes: Each infrastructure supported innovative projects that led to notable findings and advancements in their respective fields. For instance, projects ranged from exploring neuromuscular adaptations in increased gravity to leveraging natural language processing techniques for monitoring mental health in elderly populations. These projects highlight the project's commitment to advancing knowledge and developing practical solutions through TA.

Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration: A common theme across the infrastructures is the emphasis on stakeholder engagement and collaboration. Projects utilized living lab methodologies to involve various stakeholders, including end-users, researchers, industry partners, and public organizations. This collaborative approach facilitated the co-creation of solutions and the integration of diverse perspectives into the research process.

Impact on Health and Wellbeing: The TA projects collectively contributed to improving health and wellbeing, demonstrating the tangible impacts of the research conducted. From enhancing physical rehabilitation outcomes to improving mental health monitoring, the projects addressed critical health challenges, showcasing the potential of TA to effect positive change.

Opportunities for Future Research: The report also identifies opportunities for future research and collaboration, emphasizing the potential for scaling and replicating successful projects across different regions. This forward-looking perspective highlights the project's role in fostering innovation and facilitating knowledge exchange within the global research community.

Challenges and Recommendations: While celebrating successes, the report also acknowledges challenges encountered, such as ethical considerations and technological limitations. Recommendations for addressing these challenges include enhancing communication channels, streamlining administrative processes, and fostering greater international collaboration.

Key Points Considered

- The significance of harmonizing methodologies and standards across living labs to facilitate comparative research and collaboration.
- The importance of open innovation ecosystems and the living lab methodology in engaging stakeholders and co-creating solutions.
- The role of digital technologies and natural language processing in addressing health challenges, particularly in vulnerable populations like older adults.

- The need for continuous stakeholder engagement and the integration of user feedback into the development and refinement of health interventions.

Below is a table summarizing the main findings and conclusions for each research infrastructure involved in the VITALISE D8.2 Final report on Transnational Access 1:

Table 9. Summary of main findings and conclusions for research infrastructure

Research Infrastructure	Main Findings	Conclusions
AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advanced understanding of neuromuscular adaptations in increased gravity. - Developed protocols for sensorimotor processing analysis in higher G-gradients. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential for new treatments and interventions for various pathologies. - Highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange.
THOMAS MORE Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimized algorithms for Dynaback shirt, improving ergonomic assessment. - Collected valuable data for workplace ergonomics and risk assessment. - The relationship between physical activity levels, functional capacity and pain, and quality of life in middle-aged woman was investigated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrated the efficacy of integrating technology for ergonomic assessments. - Recommended future research to include additional measurements and explore broader applications. - A digital physical activity intervention for middle-aged, menopausal women will be developed targeting an increase in physical activity. This may decrease menopausal symptoms and improve quality of life. It may also reduce women’s risk and/or prevent the onset of a number of chronic health conditions such as coronary heart disease.
GAIA- Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparative analysis on climate change impact on wellbeing. - Engaged stakeholders in co-creation sessions for public space usage analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Underlined the role of living labs in addressing societal and environmental challenges. - Emphasized the need for continued exploration of nature-based solutions for climate adaptation and community wellbeing.
INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explored NLP techniques for monitoring mental health in older adults. - Developed methodologies for mood identification and audio pattern recognition for emotion detection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlighted the potential of technology in non-invasive mental health monitoring. - Stressed the importance of ethical considerations and the involvement of mental health professionals in research.

<p>LAUREA-Laurea Simulated Hospital</p>	<p>New Service Development and Innovative Business Models lectures/group discussions (observing teaching/student presentations) and implementation of Laurea’s Learning by Developing pedagogical model</p>	<p>- Laurea Simulated Hospital are inferred to align with the overall objectives of VITALISE in fostering innovation, stakeholder engagement, and the development of practical health solutions through living labs.</p>
<p>McGill-CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab</p>	<p>- Research focused on improving participation and engagement of older adults in cultural and artistic activities, using audio-guided visual search technologies. - Studies on privacy and data protection challenges in the context of the Internet of Things (IoT) for mental health.</p>	<p>- Projects underscored the importance of tailored interventions to increase cultural engagement among older adults, showing potential to improve mental and physical well-being. - Highlighted the critical need for considering ethical and privacy aspects in the development and implementation of health technologies.</p>

This table reflects a synthesized view of the key outcomes and insights derived from the various research infrastructures involved in the VITALISE project's Transnational Access activities. It underscores the diverse yet focused efforts across the consortium to advance health and wellbeing through innovative research, technology integration, and collaborative methodologies.

5 Annexes

Below we present the After-TA Evaluation Questionnaire:

T3 AFTER TA EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE (MANDATORY)

Fields marked with * are mandatory. ✕

Disclaimer ✕

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Dear researcher,

Thank you very much for participating in our Vitalise Transnational Access.

We highly appreciate you taking the time to reply to this mandatory questionnaire as it will help us continue improving the content of the Transnational Access for future participants. Completion of the questionnaire will take approximately 5-10 minutes.

The questionnaire is **not anonymous**. The next set of questions, comprising the sections Transnational Access, Living lab collaboration and Vitalise products, invite you to reflect on your journey and provide feedback on the Transnational Access.

Kind regards,

The Vitalise consortium

* **Name of the researcher filling the questionnaire** [Open question]

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TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

- * 1. How likely are you to recommend the Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)?

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

- * 2. How well were your expectations regarding the Transnational Access met?

- +2 TA output was much higher than expected
 +1 TA output was somewhat higher than expected
 0 TA output was as expected
 -1 TA output was somewhat lower than expected
 -2 TA output was much lower than expected

- * 3. How useful is the inclusion of a Fast Track Training program during Transnational Access? (0 not useful - 10 very useful)

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

- * 4. What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access? [Open question]

- * 5. Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access? [Open question]

LIVING LAB COLLABORATION

6. Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality. If services are not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column. [partly open question]

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Methodological support and guidance	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

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Other, namely ...

* **7A. Please select the research infrastructure(s) you have visited.** Multiple answers are possible.

- LICALAB / LiCalab Older Adults Homes
- LICALAB / MOBILAB & Care – Motion lab
- LICALAB / Thomas More Experience lab
- AUTH / AUTH Living Environment simulation
- AUTH / AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
- AUTH / AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
- AIT / AIT Technology Experience Lab
- TREABAG / Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab
- GAIA / GAIA and Smart Spaces
- GAIA / GAIA Ozean Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room
- INTARS / INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
- McGill / McGill-UDEM-CRIR Living Lab
- UPM / LifeSpace by UPM
- LAUREA / Laurea Simulated Hospital
- LAUREA / Laurea Activity Living Lab

* **7B. What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study?** [Open question – this question should be presented for all RI selected]

* **7C. What weaknesses in [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? (These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity).** [Open question - this question should be presented for all RI selected]

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VITALISE PRODUCTS

8. How often did you use any of the following Vitalise products during your Transnational Access?

	0 - Never	1 - Once	2- Several times	3 - Weekly	4 - Daily
* Data Tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Panel Management tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise website	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise Wiki page	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

9. Please rate the following products in terms of user friendliness. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Panel Management tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise website	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise Wiki page	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

10. Please rate the following products in terms of usefulness as it relates to your research process. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Panel Management tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise website	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Vitalise Wiki page	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

* 11. In what way did any of these products affect your Transnational Access work? (for example, saved me time, greater accuracy, etc.)
[Open question]

12. How much do you anticipate needing the following services or products in your future work? (Very low probability – very high probability).

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Methodological support and guidance	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Data tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
* Panel management tool	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

13. Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research? [Open question]

14. Any additional comments you would like to share with us? [Open question]

Thank you very much!

Submit